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Deliverable D4.3 Models for vertical descriptor adaptation

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Description</i>		
API	Application Programming Interface	TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
CtxB	Context Blueprint	UE	User Equipment
DCM	Data Collection Manager	VL	Virtual Link
DCM	Data Collection Manager	VLD	Virtual Link descriptors
DCS	Data Collection and Storage	VNF	Virtual Network Function
EBB	Experiment Blueprint Builder	VNFD	VNF Descriptor
EEM	Experiment Execution Manager	VNFFGD	VNF Forwarding Graph descriptors
ELM	Experiment Lifecycle Manager	VSB	Vertical Service Blueprint
ENC	Experiment NSD Composer		
ExpB	Experiment Blueprint		
ExpD	Experiment Descriptor		
IFA	InterFaces and Architecture		
ISG	Industry Specification Group		
IWF	InterWorking Framework		
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation		
KPI	Key Performance Indicator		
MSO	Multi-Site Network Orchestrator		
NBI	North-Bound Interface		
NFV	Network Function Virtualization		
NFVO	NFV Orchestrator		
NS	Network Service		
NSD	Network Service Descriptor		
PNF	Physical Network Function		
PNFD	PNF Descriptor		
RAN	Radio Access Network		
RC	Runtime Configurator		
SOL	SOLution		
SSH	Secure SHell		
TC	Test Case		
TcB	Test Case Blueprint		

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Executive Summary

This deliverable contributes to a concrete step forward in the 5G EVE end-to-end facility implementation, by providing details about how tools described in D4.1 [1] and firstly integrated together in D4.2 [2] are further improved in order to deliver advanced automation capabilities to the overall facility for the preparation and configuration of an experiment. The focus of this deliverable is represented by the chains of data models transformation that allow converting high-level templates presented to the vertical users (the blueprints) into low-level configuration files and actionable items. Since such transformation process happens in the background, within the portal backend, in a completely automatic fashion, it allows simplifying the interaction of vertical users with the 5G EVE end-to-end facility, without sacrificing flexibility and possibilities for experiment personalization. Towards that goal, this document specifies how some of the key components in the 5G EVE Portal, namely the Experiment Blueprint Builder, the Portal Catalogue, the Experiment Lifecycle Manager, and the Experiment Execution Manager, already sketched in D4.1 and D4.2, closely interact in order to provide this level of automation in the definition and configuration of an experiment, including not only functional aspects of the experiment, but also configurations related to collection of metrics and validation of key performance indicators. In this document we introduce an additional component, called Experiment Network Service Descriptor Composer, which provides a high level of automation in one of the most critical steps of an experiment preparation, that is the building of a ETSI-compliant network service descriptor to be fed into the InterWorking Framework, i.e. the component in the 5G EVE infrastructure that directly interfaces with different site facilities. While in the first release of the portal such a step was carried out manually during the experiment definition phase, now it becomes completely automatic and it is no longer needed to be performed by the vertical users, thus lowering the usability bar of the 5G EVE facilities as well as the possibility of mistakes in an error-prone procedure. All these activities are carried out in the framework of the Task T4.3 and are integrated into those described in T4.1 and prototyped in T4.2.

1 Introduction

The 5G EVE project's main goal is to create a bridge between two worlds: the vertical industries and the ICT actors. This bridge is implemented in a 5G end-to-end facility that exposes communications and computing resources hosted in the trial sites through abstract, platform-independent models that hide the complexity of specific technologies. Vertical industries leverage these simplified and abstract models to easily access 5G-enabled resources in order to test and validate their applications.

The vertical-centric approach, based on layers of abstraction, makes use of models that describe services, service templates, configuration, metrics to collect, and tests to run. Models do not specify how to achieve something, but just the desired object, goal, or status. From this viewpoint, the usage of these models can be considered a way to implement the so-called intent-based networking (IBN) approach [3][4][5][6], as already sketched in D4.1 with intent-based interface towards vertical players [1]. Dedicated software components deployed in the 5G EVE portal cater for the translation and adaptation of models from one layer of abstraction to another and vice-versa, while others take care of implementing actions and operations to realize what is described in the model. Given the complexity of this requirement in a platform implemented on an infrastructure based on Network Function Virtualization (NFV) capabilities, it is convenient that each component handles one specific aspect of the adaptation from higher layers to lower layers. On the other hand, providing abstraction and usability could result in more constrained features and scenarios exposed to verticals, trading off usability for flexibility. To prevent that possible issue, the components' design has been carried on with the requirement of always allowing for some level of customization to the verticals whenever that is not compromising the main functionality. The overall process of designing and executing an experiment is thus carried out by means of a model-based approach, starting from models with the highest level of abstraction, which are those presented to the vertical users, and ending with the most detailed one, which are fed into the 5G EVE platform to enforce device configuration and experiment execution. *The description of the overall process of model transformation and adaptations into configurations and actionable items is the goal of this deliverable.* Such data models have been already partially sketched in previous deliverables D4.1 [1] and D5.2 [7]. They are summarized in Table 1 for easing the reader effort and then explained more in detail in Section 2, where we provide a comprehensive view of all their features, since their knowledge is fundamental for the understanding of the different processes presented in this document.

Table 1: Data models

Type of model	Short description
Vertical service blueprint (VSB)	A VSB is a high-level information model for a template of a network service. It includes a high-level description of the atomic functional components of the service and their interconnection and contains a set of parameters that can be used to customize the service.
Context blueprint (CtxB)	A CtxB is a high-level information model for a template of a re-usable component that applies some contextual condition on the vertical service, like artificial delay or artificial background traffic.
Experiment blueprint (ExpB)	An ExpB is a high-level information model for a template of an experiment to be executed on the 5G EVE platform. The ExpB is created from the composition of a VSB and a custom set of CtxBs, and it includes all of their parameters. Furthermore, the ExpB includes information about monitoring, key performance indicators (KPIs), and tests to run.
Network service descriptor (NSD)	NSDs are detailed information data models for all the network entities involved in a network service, including their interconnections.

	They can be technology agnostic (ETSI NFV-IFA 014) or implementation specific (ETSI NFV-SOL 001).
Experiment descriptor (ExpD)	The ExpD is the descriptor obtained from the ExpB when filled with <i>actual values</i> of parameters and configuration during the preparation of the experiment execution.

At the highest level of abstraction, the 5G EVE platform users interact with the blueprint, an abstract model to describe a network service template together with the description of metrics and other information. In particular, Experiment Blueprints (ExpB) are used to describe an experiment template involving the vertical's service. The experiment is aimed at validating some key performance indicators (KPIs), also defined in the ExpB, while executing some controlled tests on the service. From this viewpoint, the experiments extend the concept of service, including all features relevant to the characterization of operational conditions (called "context") and those relevant to metrics to collect and KPIs to validate. The network service expressed by any blueprint is described in higher detail in a more complex model, standardized by the ETSI Industry Specification Group (ISG) NFV in the ETSI GS NFV-IFA 014 [8] and NFV-IFA 011 [9] documents. These models, called ETSI NFV-IFA Network Service Descriptors (NSDs), are complete in the detailed representation of a network service, but remain technology agnostic. This means that they need to be translated into descriptors specific of NFV technologies, like those standardized by ETSI [10], thus providing another layer of abstraction between the 5G EVE platform and the specific NFV technologies adopted in trial sites, as well as a potential degree of freedom for future adoption of this approach in another scenario.

Since the ETSI NFV-IFA model is quite complex, the 5G EVE platform guides the experiment developer¹ in the construction of their experiments, providing tools and procedures to automate many of the steps, without requiring to directly interact with the descriptor model. In this deliverable, we will present the Experiment Network Service Descriptor Composer, a tool specifically designed to manipulate blueprints and their related NSDs to automatically compose new experiments and generate the relevant customized NSDs, describing not only the service but also the associated context conditions at lower level of abstraction. Thus, the experiment developer is just invited to select the blueprint associated to the service to test (Vertical Service Blueprint, VSB, see [1]) and a number of context conditions (delay, background traffic, etc.) modelled by means of Context Blueprints (CtxBs).

The blueprints and NSDs are stored and managed by the Portal Catalogue that also provides a two-way translation feature from the ETSI NFV-IFA model to the ETSI GS NFV-SOL 001 [10] model. The latter is a reference implementation of the ETSI NFV-IFA model using TOSCA Simple profile in YAML [11], and it is understandable by the Multi-Site Network Orchestrator (described in deliverables D3.2 [12], D3.3[13]), which, in turn, interacts with the trial sites participating in the 5G EVE infrastructure.

Apart from the network service to be deployed, the ExpB includes other sections to provide a complete definition of the experiment. During the design of an experiment, the Experiment Blueprint Builder, a graphical wizard in the 5G EVE portal, guides the experiment developer in the construction, step by step, of a new ExpB. The tool allows the user to define metrics to be collected, KPIs to be validated, and test cases to be executed on the new experiment. During the preparation phase and the execution phase of the experiment these elements, which are defined at a high level, are adapted into actions and configurations for components laying at lower levels of the 5G EVE infrastructure.

Relevant metrics, both from the vertical service and from the infrastructure, are declared in the ExpB with a simple, human-understandable model. A dedicated component in the portal, the Experiment Lifecycle Manager,

¹ The basic blueprint associated to the service (VSB) and the relevant basic NSD are provided to the 5G EVE Portal by the experiment developer, a user with some knowledge about the 5G EVE infrastructure and some expertise about NFV network service modelling. Moreover, he interacts with the vertical to gather information about the details of the target service. See D4.1 [1] for a complete list of roles for the users interacting with the 5G EVE portal.

takes care of configuring the data collection framework of the 5G EVE infrastructure to enable the collection and the subsequent consumption from tools for analysis and validation.

Finally, in order to provide more flexibility in the testing phase, the experiment can be customized through service parameters and customizable test scripts. Each combination creates a new experiment, to let the vertical experimenter have different versions of the experiment and validate their KPIs under different conditions. The Experiment Execution Manager is the tool in charge of the translation of this information into VNF configurations and command executions.

In this deliverable we are going to describe the tools involved in the model manipulation, translation, and transformation necessary to adapt vertical requirements to the particular technologies deployed on the 5G EVE end to end facility. Section 2 will introduce the main data models of the 5G EVE platform. In Section 3, we are going to describe the whole process of data model transformation, moving from more abstract to more technology specific models, and identifying the main modules in charge of carrying out these transformations. Section 4 contains a detailed description of the tools involved in the model manipulation and their operation. Section 5 will provide a concrete example of all the model transformations for a specific vertical use-case implemented in the 5G EVE project. Finally, Section 6 will present the conclusions and final observations.

2 Data models

The main data models used in 5G EVE platform are described in deliverable D4.1 [1] and D5.2 [7] and briefly listed in Table 1. In this section, we recap the main concepts of the models to ease the reader in the understanding of this document, providing the description of their main fields, useful to understand the data model manipulations described in Section 4.

2.1 Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB)

A VSB is a high-level information model for a template of a network service. It includes a high-level description of the atomic functional components of the service and their interconnections. Furthermore, it contains a set of parameters that can be used to customize the service. Figure 1 shows a graphical representation of a sample, generic network service defined by a VSB.

Figure 1: Representation of a network service generated from a VSB.

The green boxes are the atomic functional components that can consist of a virtual network function (VNF), a physical network function (PNF), or even of a nested VSB. The black connectors are the endpoints, also called connection points. The blue ovals are the connectivity services, the networks to which the atomic components are attached to. As in the simple example shown here, a connectivity service for management is always provided in the 5G EVE platform and all the atomic components are attached to it. In fact, a management network is necessary for the various configuration to be applied to those components at various stages during the experiment starting phase (day-0, -1, or -2 configuration²). Finally, the red circles are the external endpoints to access the network service from an external network, also called Service Access Points (SAP). Table 2 reports the fields composing a VSB with their short description.

² Each lifecycle stage targets specific configurations in the VNF/PNF/NS. These are: management setup during instantiation (Day-0), service initialization right after instantiation (Day-1) and re-configuration during runtime (Day-2). More details can be found in [32].

Table 2: Vertical Service Blueprint fields with relevant description

Field	Description
blueprintId	Unique Identifier for the VSB.
version	A version number.
name	Name for the VSB.
description	Short description of the VSB.
parameters	List of parameters. The list provides for each parameter its name, type, description, and the field of applicability.
atomicComponents	List of atomic functional components (i.e., network functions and virtual applications in general) needed to implement the VSB.
endPoints	Specification of connection endpoints. They can be internal or external.
connectivityServices	List of virtual links and their relevant end points. Virtual links describe how the atomic functional components are connected.
serviceSequence	Description of how traffic flows among VNFs, supporting also multicast scenarios.
configurableParameters	Parameters that can be configured by the user for a specific instance of service derived from the given blueprint.
applicationMetrics	List of metrics that this service can provide. Metrics reported here are strictly application related. No network metrics are included.
compatibleSites	List of 5G EVE sites where the vertical service can be deployed.
compatibleContextBlueprint	List of IDs of the blueprints defining the experiment execution contexts that are compatible with the given vertical service.

A VSB YAML file example can be found in Annex A. As shown in the annex, the topology information is provided by means of a textual description consisting of the list of atomicComponents, endPoints and connectivityServices. A graphical representation like that of Figure 1 is provided by the Portal to the experiment developer by processing this set of information.

2.2 Context Blueprint (CtxB)

A Context Blueprint (CtxB) is like a VSB but it describes a template for network elements used to define an operational context for the network service. CtxBs are used to define experimental conditions for the service described in the VSB, like artificial background traffic, artificial delay, packet loss, and similar. Like the VSB, the CtxB can include some parameters to customize its components.

The 5G EVE platform will include some generic context elements that can be applied to the majority of network services. Experiment developers can compile additional CtxBs specifically related to a single network service. For example, given a VSB that includes a cloud application, the experiment developer can create a specific traffic generator that emulates the behaviour of one or multiple users. Table 3 reports the fields composing a CtxB with their short description.

Table 3: Context Blueprint fields with relevant description

Field	Description
blueprintId	Unique Identifier for the CtxB.
Version	A version number.
Name	Name for the CtxB.

description	Short description of the CtxB.
parameters	List of parameters. The list provides for each parameter its name, type, description, and the field of applicability.
atomicComponents	List of atomic functional components (i.e., network functions and virtual applications in general) needed to implement the CtxB.
endPoints	Specification of connection endpoints. They can be internal or external.
connectivityServices	List of virtual links and their relevant end points. Virtual links describe how the atomic functional components are connected.
configurableParameters	Parameters that can be configured by the user for a specific instance of execution context derived from the given blueprint.
applicationMetrics	List of metrics that this execution context can provide. Metrics reported here are strictly application related. No network metrics are included.
compatibleSites	List of 5G EVE sites where the vertical service can be deployed.
compositionStrategy	The strategy to be used by the Experiment Blueprint Builder (EBB) to compose this CtxB with a VSB. One of PASS_THROUGH or CONNECT.

A CtxB YAML file example can be found in Annex E.

2.3 Experiment Blueprint (ExpB)

An ExpB describes a template for an experiment to be executed on the 5G EVE platform. The ExpB is created from the composition of a VSB and a custom set of CtxBs and it includes all of their parameters. Furthermore, the ExpB includes information about monitoring, KPIs, and tests to run.

The ExpB describes an experiment with a specific network topology that shall remain unchanged during its execution. The parameters allow for some, but limited customization of the experiment. However, the information about the network topology obtained by the composition of a VSB with a set of CtxBs is not provided in the ExpB, but it is included in the associated NSD. The main goal of the ExpB is rather to specify the elements to compose and type of experiment to carry out on that obtained topology.

The ExpB is compiled by the experiment developer with the support of automated tools. The tools will take as input a VSB and a selected set of CtxBs. Then, they combine the selected elements respecting some constraints and generates the resulting experiment. As a result, from a source single VSB a number of different ExpBs can be generated. Once generated, the ExpB is persistently stored in the 5G EVE platform. Table 4 reports the fields composing an ExpB with their short description.

Table 4: Experiment Blueprint fields with relevant description

Field	Description
expBlueprintId	Unique Identifier for the ExpB.
version	A version number.
name	Name for the ExpB.
description	Short description of the ExpB.
vsBlueprintId	The identifier of the VSB this experiment was built from.
ctxBlueprintIds	List of the identifiers of the CtxBs this experiment was built from.
tcBlueprintIds	List of the identifiers of the TcBs this experiment includes. Test cases are parameter-based templates that describe the concrete actions to be executed during the experiment.

sites	The trial sites involved in this experiment. This determines the radio coverage for this experiment.
infrastructureMetrics	List of infrastructure metrics to be monitored for this experiment.
kpis	List of KPIs to be validated for this experiment. They can be both application and network KPIs.

An ExpB YAML file example can be found in Annex G. As a result of the composition rules and of the fact that topology information is not included in the ExpB, usually the ExpB is a more compact model than the associated VSB.

2.4 Experiment Descriptor (ExpD)

An ExpD defines a specific experiment for the 5G EVE platform. All the parameters for the experiment are set and all the information to execute it are provided.

The ExpD is generated from an ExpB. During the experiment preparation phase, the experimenter selects a VSB and subsequently one of the available ExpB designed by the experiment developer. The experimenter is going to be asked to fill the parameters of the ExpB. The procedure is concluded with the generation and storage of the ExpD. Some metadata can be attached to the ExpD with information about the scheduling of the experiment. Table 5 reports the fields composing an ExpD with their short description.

Table 5: Experiment Descriptor fields with relevant description

Field	Description
expDescriptorId	Unique Identifier for the ExpD.
version	A version number.
name	Name for the ExpD.
description	Short description of the ExpD.
expBlueprintId	The identifier of the ExpB this experiment descriptor was built from.
vsDescriptorId	ID of the Vertical Service Descriptor describing the vertical service to be deployed to run this experiment. It provides the full specification of the parameters related to the vertical service, as defined in its originating blueprint.
ctxDescriptorIds	List of the IDs of the components associated to the experiment execution contexts (i.e. the Context Descriptors) to be deployed to run this experiment. They provide the full specification of the parameters related to the contexts, as defined in their originating blueprints.
testCaseDescriptorIds	List of the IDs of the test case descriptors defining the steps to run this experiment. They provide the full specification of the values of the variable parameters to be added in the experiment scripts, as defined in their originating blueprints.
kpiThresholds	List of thresholds for the KPIs defined in the originating experiment blueprint. They define the criteria to evaluate the results of the experiment.

2.5 Test Case Blueprint (TcB)

The Experiment Blueprint (ExpB) includes a list of Test Case Blueprints (TcB). A TcB is a customizable template that describes the actions to be performed during the execution of the experiment. Actions are collected in a script and user parameters and infrastructure variables can be used to customize the script execution. Table 6 reports the fields composing an ExpB with their short description.

Table 6: Test Case Blueprint fields with relevant description

Field	Description
testcaseBlueprintId	Unique Identifier for the Test Case Blueprint
Script	Source code of the script to be executed
userParameters	Mapping of script variables to user parameters for the test customization
infrastructureParameters	Mapping of script variables to infrastructure parameters for the dynamic test configuration based on the specific NS related to the experiment (e.g., IP addresses)

“userParameters” and “infrastructureParameters” are used to make the TcB customizable, dynamic, and reusable. “userParameters” are used to inject the value of some parameters into the test script to be executed. As an example, we can consider a Test Case Blueprint associated to an experiment to evaluate the performance of a network service under the effect of artificial background traffic. A trivial user parameter is the amount of background traffic to apply during the experiment. The “userParameters” field will have a key-value pair to map the parameter name to the variable name used in the “script” source code to control the amount of background traffic.

The “infrastructureParameters” is used to make the TcB applicable to many network services. Considering again the example used before, the application of artificial background traffic trivially needs two endpoints to be applied, a source and a sink. The “infrastructureParameters” will then include the necessary key-value pairs to inject in the test script the IP addresses to be used as source and sink for the background traffic.

2.6 ETSI NFV-IFA 014 and NFV-IFA 011 models

The ETSI ISG NFV has put considerable effort in the definition of a reference architecture for NFV. Furthermore, they defined data models, namely descriptors, for all the network entities in the NFV framework. A high level, technology agnostic description of the structure and composing fields of each entity is given in NFV-IFA (InterFaces and Architecture) deliverables. More specifically NFV-IFA 011 [9] defines what is included in a Virtual Network Function Descriptor (VNFD) and how to build a VNF Package, which is an archive with the VNFD plus other files (metadata). NFV-IFA 014 [8] defines what is included in a Network Service Descriptor (NSD). As shown in subsequent Figure 12, the NSD references by means of their IDs a list of VNFDs and Physical Network Function Descriptors (PNFDs) involved in the definition of the service. Furthermore, it includes Virtual Link Descriptors (VLD) defining the virtual or physical networks used to connect the VNFs and PNFs.

The NFV-IFA models are very detailed and provide all the means to leverage the advantages of a virtualized, dynamic, and automated environment (i.e., cloud based). An NSD is not a mere text-based description of how a set of network functions are connected, but it also includes the definition of several resource requirement profiles for the deployment of the service and scaling possibilities of its elements. The NSD is given the power to define multiple flavours of the network service, even with different topologies. For example, one network topology can define one instance of a VNF while the second one rewrites the topology to include two instances of the same VNF and proper connections to implement horizontal scaling and load-balancing.

This “sizing” of the network service is realized by means of the concepts of “Flavour” and “Instantiation Level”. The same concepts are also applied in the scope of VNFD and VLD, allowing for extreme flexibility in the description of how to deploy every component. The NSD references and reuses the flavours and levels defined in VNFD and VLD in order to respect the separation of concerns and each model can be kept as short as possible.

In the NSD model, the combination of a Network Service Deployment Flavour (NsDF) and a Network Service Instantiation Level (NsLevel) defines a variant of the network service with specific resource requirements and topology, ready to be deployed. The NsDF specifies the VNF, PNF and Virtual Link profiles to be used. Profiles declare the amount of resources required to deploy the referenced element. For example, for a VNF, we can define a profile to be deployed with 2 CPUs and another one with 4 CPUs. VNF profiles also describe how they are connected to the Virtual Link profiles. The NsDF includes a list of NsLevel information elements. Each NsLevel selects a subset of the profiles defined in the NsDF to realize a variant of the Network Service. For

VNF profiles, it also defines the number of instances to be deployed, implementing horizontal scaling. For Virtual Link profiles, it defines the bitrate requirements.

2.7 Translation Rules

A Translation Rule is an information model used to set, in a simple manner, the size of the experiment at deployment time in terms of computing resources. The VSB includes a set of service parameters, like for example the expected number of user equipment units to be served. The experimenter can set values for these service parameters during the experiment preparation phase. A Translation rule maps ranges of service parameter values to a single combination of NsDf and NsLevel that, as we have seen in the previous section, are the mean to define a variant of the network service described by the NSD.

The information model of Translation Rules has been introduced in deliverable D4.1 [1]. Table 7 shows the detailed description of all the fields in the model.

Thanks to the “input” field, a combination of multiple parameter ranges can be associated to the network service variant identified by “nsdId”, “nsFlavourId”, “nsInstantiationLevelId”.

Table 7: Translation Rule fields with relevant description

Field	Description
input	List of value ranges associated to a parameter expressed with a minimum value and a maximum value. Each item in the list is composed of “parameterId”, “minValue”, “maxValue”.
nsdId	The identifier of the NSD referenced by this Translation Rule.
nsFlavourId	The identifier of the NsDF referenced by this Translation Rule.
nsInstantiationLevelId	The identifier of the NsLevel referenced by this Translation Rule.

3 Overall process of data model transformation

The design and realization of a 5G end-to-end infrastructure with NFV capabilities is a complex task per se. The additional requirement to make it easy to use for vertical users even adds other challenges. Abstracting concepts from many specific technologies and making complex configurations understandable and usable from non-expert users require a lot of effort in smart algorithms for automation and transformation.

Figure 2: High-level scheme for overall data model transformation process.

5G EVE adopted a model-based approach, preferring declarative languages over imperative ones. The information models designed and implemented by the project express a goal or desired state for the platform and the platform itself transforms these models into actions and more detailed and lower level configurations. Various tools are involved in the manipulation, translation and adaptation of these models on different levels of abstraction. Figure 2 shows a high-level workflow of the model transformations happening in the upper layers (most

abstracted) of the infrastructure. Each software component takes care of a specific aspect of the information contained in the models. The separation of concerns is an important principle in software design that enables the achievement of modularity and reusability.

Figure 2 shows a high-level workflow starting from blueprints, the most abstract models available in 5G EVE, and descending to more specific, technology-aware layers. Two main chains of transformations can be identified, the one related to the transformation of ETSI NFV NSD models (left) and the one related to the remaining information needed to complete the description of an experiment (right), like metrics to be collected, KPIs to be validated, and tests to be executed with the relevant configuration. The workflow is conceptual and not necessarily chronological, meaning that two chained operations do not have to happen one immediately or directly after the other. Other procedures of the 5G EVE platform can happen between one model transformation step and the other. For a more complete overview of design, preparation, and execution phases of an experiment, please refer to deliverable D4.1 [1] and workflows therein.

The chain on the left of Figure 2, shows the transformations applied to the NSD, the information model that describes in detail the network topology of a service or of an experiment. Each NSD is associated to a blueprint, which describes its network topology at a higher layer of abstraction, with less details, but at the same time adds some contextual information related to the 5G EVE platform. The information model named as Translation Rule contains information on how to map some elements of the NSD to elements of the related blueprint. The 5G EVE platform offers the possibility for its users to generate customized experiments by composing a vertical service with some modular, reusable components called contexts. The composition is automated as much as possible, in order to free the user from the task of writing or re-writing experiment models manually. Taking as input a VSB, a list of Context Blueprints (CtxB), their related NSDs and the translation rules, the *Experiment NSD Composer* (ENC) tool is able to automatically generate a new NSD together with its new set of translation rules. The resulting NSD, in ETSI NFV-IFA 014 format, is in turn onboarded to the *Portal Catalogue*. This component verifies the resources and requirements stated in the NSD against the information retrieved from the whole 5G platform, including all the trial sites. If the newly created NSD is valid, it is translated by the Portal Catalogue into the ETSI NFV-SOL 001 format, which represents the ETSI standard for technology aware descriptors. The latter is onboarded to the Multi-Site Catalogue that in turn, is in charge of the translation into the specific model of each NFV orchestrator. For the complete workflow of the onboarding operations, please refer to deliverable D4.1 [1].

Anyway, other information is necessary for the complete realization of the experiment on the 5G EVE platform, which requires to implement the other transformation chain. On the right side of Figure 2 we can see the chain of transformations for managing metrics, KPIs and tests scripts to be executed. The *Experiment Blueprint Builder* (EBB) provides the experiment developer with a simple, step-by-step graphical interface to easily define the just mentioned information. At the end of this process, the EBB generates an Experiment Blueprint (ExpB) containing all the definitions in a structured format, understandable by other software components of the 5G EVE platform. As the ExpB is just a template, during the preparation of the experiment execution, the experimenter provides actual values of service parameters and configuration creating an Experiment Descriptor (ExpD). The couple made up of ExpB and ExpD identifies an instance of an experiment. During the experiment execution, two components are involved, the *Experiment Lifecycle Manager* (ELM) and the *Experiment Execution Manager* (EEM). The former transforms the declarative information about metrics into actual configuration for the Data Collection framework of 5G EVE. The latter takes care of transforming the data stored in the information models into the Day-2 VNF configuration and of the execution of tests. Table 8 summarizes, for each component involved in model transformations in Figure 1, the component role, the input/output parameters, the interactions with other component and (eventually) interaction with verticals.

Table 8: Main components involved in model transformations with relevant description³

Component	Aspect	Short Description
Experiment Blueprint Builder (EBB)	Role	The EBB is a sub-component of the 5G EVE Portal that provides a graphical user interface to help the experiment developer in creating an ExpB with guided, incremental steps. Furthermore, it wraps all the communications with the Portal Catalogue, showing to the experiment developer VSB, CtxB and other data elements already available in the 5G EVE infrastructure and ensuring that the creation of the ExpB is always consistent. The workflows and interactions of the EBB are presented in deliverable D4.1 [1], while the design implementation and usage are discussed in deliverable D4.2 [2].
	Input	VSB, list of CtxBs, metrics, KPIs, test scripts
	Output	ExpB
	Interactions with other tools	ENC, Portal Catalogue
	Interaction with Verticals	Yes (experiment developer)
Experiment NSD Composer (ENC)	Role	The ENC provides features to automatically manipulate and generate an NSD in the ETSI NFV-IFA 014 model. This component automatically composes a vertical service with a list of context elements that can be considered as attachable modules. As input, it takes a VSB with the associated NSD, plus a list of Context Blueprints (CtxB) also with their associated NSD. The composition of the two inputs generates a new NSD, to be associated with an Experiment Blueprint (ExpB) that describes an experiment template. The goal of this tool is to support the EBB in the easy and automatic creation of several different experiments for a single vertical service, enabling more flexibility for the vertical user. Furthermore, it implements code and VNF re-usability thanks to the concept of CtxB.
	Input	VSB with associated NSD, list of CtxBs with associated NSDs, Translation Rules
	Output	Composed NSD, updated Translation Rules
	Interactions with other tools	EBB

³The description, input, and output, are related to model transformations and adaptations. Also, the table only lists interactions among components discussed in this document. Each component may provide more functionalities in the 5G EVE platform, out of the scope of this document.

	Interaction with Verticals	-
Portal Catalogue	Role	The Portal Catalogue is in charge of storing and managing all the blueprints and the related NSDs, VNFDs and PNFDs. More details about the design and implementation of the portal catalogue can be found in deliverable D4.1 [1]. Furthermore, the Portal Catalogue is able to translate NSDs, VNFDs, and PNFDs, from the ETSI NFV-IFA model to the NFV-SOL 001 model [10] and vice-versa. The output of the transformation is a more-detailed, lower-level representation of NSDs, VNFDs, and PNFDs to be fed as input to the Multi-Site Catalogue in the Interworking Framework, a lower layer of the 5G EVE platform. The design and implementation of this component are described in deliverables D3.2 [12] and D3.3 [13].
	Input	NSD in ETSI NFV-IFA 014 format
	Output	NSD in ETSI NFV-SOL 001 format
	Interactions with other tools	EBB, Portal GUI, Multi-Site Catalogue
	Interaction with Verticals	-
Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELM)	Role	The Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELM) is the component in charge of the creation and termination of an experiment execution and in the allocation of the necessary resources. Furthermore, this component takes care of translating the metrics definitions in the ExpB into actual configuration for the Data Collection Manager (DCM). The latter is a publish/subscribe system with data organized in “topics”. The ELM takes care of the creation of the topics and enables the subscription to them from other components, enabling data consumption. All the workflows and interactions of the ELM with other components are described in deliverables D5.2 [7] and D4.2 [2].
	Input	ExpB, ExpD
	Output	Metric topics, subscription notifications
	Interactions with other tools	Portal Catalogue, EEM, DCM
	Interaction with Verticals	-
Experiment Execution Manager (EEM)	Role	The EEM (see details in D5.2 [7]) is in charge of the Day-2 configuration of the VNFs composing a Network Service and of the execution of tests. The ExpB and ExpD models provide a simple

		but complete representation of this information, allowing the experimenter to customize their experiment. The EEM transforms the model information in actual, ready to execute commands and actions to be applied on the VNFs. The direct interaction with the VNFs is delegated to the Runtime Configurator (RC), a component of the Interworking Framework (see D3.2 [12] and D3.3 [13]).
	Input	ExpB, ExpD
	Output	VNF Day-2 configuration, test scripts execution
	Interactions with other tools	ELM, Runtime Configurator
	Interaction with Verticals	-

3.1 Example with a real use case

Throughout this deliverable we are going to use the Smart Transport Tracker use case as an example. The use case is developed by Ares2T, an internal participant vertical of the 5G EVE project. More details on this use-case can be found in deliverables D5.2 [7].

Experiment Description:

The Transport vertical use cases can be tested applying for a tracking and recognition service experiment where an end user, equipped with a 5G terminal, moves around a 5G covered area performing different transportation modes (e.g. walking, biking, driving a vehicle or using public transportation means) and sending the collected data from the mobile device sensors (mainly GPS, accelerometer, magnetometer and gyroscope) to a backend platform where the real-time data are elaborated to estimate the end user transportation mode.

Expected Capabilities:

A mobile network connecting the 5G terminal to the platform with the virtual machines hosting the tracking and recognition services is required. The most challenging requirements to ensure the deployment of the above described solution in the future smart cities are the high reliability and the low latency.

The VSB for this service, available in Annex A, includes the following atomic components:

- Tracker backend
- Visualization tool

The two components are connected via three connectivity services:

- Tracking mobile: network with RAN access to connect with UEs
- Tracking data: network for user data traffic
- Tracking management: network for management traffic

Figure 3: Representation of the VSB graph for the Smart Transport Tracker use case

Figure 3 shows a graphical representation for the use-case, generated by the EBB and presented to the experiment developer. The figure also shows the external endpoints to connect to the service. The “sap_tracking_mobile” is a Service Access Point (SAP) for the UEs to connect to the service, whereas the “sap_tracking_mgmt” is the SAP for controlling the VNFs.

The vertical expressed interest in testing their service under the abnormal condition of delayed data traffic coming from the UEs and under the presence of unwanted background traffic. These two conditions are generic and available in the 5G EVE through reusable CtxB. The code of these blueprints in YAML is presented in Annex E.

The EBB guides the experiment developer in the construction of the ExpB for its service use-case, applying the desired conditions. The ENC takes care of composing the NSD and translation rules. Metrics, KPIs, tests to be executed are added by the experiment developer thanks to the EBB user interface. The resulting ExpB is reported in Annex G.

Section 5 will show in detail all the phases of model transformations for the Smart Transport Tracker use-case.

4 Tools for data model transformations

This section focuses on the functional and algorithmic perspective of the proposed tools, describing the role of each tool and the relationships of other components in the portal. The source code for all the software components presented here can be found at the links reported in Table 9.

Table 9: Links to the 5G EVE GitHub code repositories

Component	URL
Experiment Blueprint Builder	Included in Portal Catalogue GUI, available at: https://github.com/nextworks-it/slicer-catalogue/tree/5geve-release/EVE_CATALOGUE_GUI
Experiment NSD Composer	https://github.com/5GEVE/-exp-nsd-composer
Portal Catalogue	https://github.com/nextworks-it/slicer-catalogue/tree/5geve-release
IFA NSD information model library	https://github.com/nextworks-it/nfv-ifa-libs/tree/feat-librefactor/NFV_MANO_LIBS_DESCRIPTOR
SOL 001 information model library	https://github.com/nextworks-it/nfv-sol-libs/tree/master/NFV_MANO_SOL001_LIBS_DESCRIPTOR
SOL 001 specific driver under the NFVO driver	https://github.com/nextworks-it/nfvo-drivers/tree/master/NFVO_CATALOGUE_SPECIFIC_DRIVERS/src/main/java/it/nextworks/nfvmno/nfvdriver/sol
Experiment Lifecycle Manager	https://github.com/nextworks-it/experiment-portal/tree/master/ExperimentLifecycleManager
Experiment Execution Manager	https://github.com/5GEVE/experiment-execution-manager

4.1 Experiment Blueprint Builder (EBB)

The EBB is a component of the Portal web GUI, already released and documented in D4.2 [2], section 1.4.3, which provides a wizard to guide the experiment developer in the definition of the different elements composing an Experiment Blueprint (ExpB). In the initial version of the portal GUI, the user had to select all the service level components of the desired experiment, i.e. Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB), Context Blueprint (CtxB), define metrics and KPIs, and had to also provide, explicitly, the NSD and the translation rules related to the NFV network service implementing the experiment. The experiment NSD must be thus compiled manually by the user.

This deliverable introduces a new component, called Experiment NSD Composer (ENC) and reported in the next section, which automates the definition of the experiment NSD starting from the NSD of its components, i.e. the NSDs associated to the VSB and to the CtxBs selected for the ExpB. In the 5G EVE Portal development roadmap, the next version of the EBB will thus be enhanced to integrate the interaction with the ENC and simplify the procedure of the ExpB definition for the experiment developer. In particular, instead of onboarding the experiment NSD and defining the related translation rules (see Figure 11 and Figure 12 in D4.2 [2]), the ENC will automatically compose the experiment NSD and the translation rules (see Figure 4). The integration between the EBB at the Portal GUI and the ENC is planned for the next 5G EVE Portal release, in June 2020. A feature of the EBB is to provide the experiment developer with a simplified topology of the VSB, in order to check it before going on with the ExpB definition. An example of generated figure is reported in Figure 3. In a future version of the EBB, we will evaluate the possibility to introduce the new feature of allowing the experiment developer to provide some additional input for specific contexts (context type CONNECT, see Section 4.2.2) by interacting with the service topology specified in the VSB. The selection could be made by clicking on the graphical elements of the vertical service graph shown in Figure 3 to simplify the choice. In any case,

this possibility would be left as optional with respect to the default configuration, in which the ENC is in charge to select the most suitable links where to attach context elements. The new feature will be discussed and reported in deliverable D4.4 [14].

4.2 Experiment NSD Composer (ENC)

The ENC is the software component in charge of the composition of NSDs. In the following sections we show its interactions with other software components in 5G EVE, the design idea behind the composition algorithm, and details about the implementation.

4.2.1 Input, output and interactions with other components

The ENC provides a REST API to offer its operations for the composition of NSDs to other components of the 5G EVE platform. A single path is offered, called “/experiments”. A REST client can send a POST request to this path to obtain a new, composed experiment. The request body, which is also the input to the composition algorithm, must contain:

- The information about a vertical service template:
 - VSB
 - associated NSD
 - translation rules
- A list of contexts to be applied to the vertical service template. Each item is made of:
 - CtxB
 - associated NSD
 - translation rules

As anticipated in the previous section in the EBB description, additional inputs can be provided for some of the contexts in the request, as the references to some elements of the VSB. The selection will be eased by means of an interactive visualization of the network topology, similar to the one shown in Figure 3. This feature is under evaluation to be included in the next release of the 5G EVE Portal and it will be reported in deliverable D4.4 [14]. Anyway, the additional input is not mandatory as the ENC is able to take some default, safe choices in the composition without the need for additional instructions. More information about the additional input parameters are discussed in the following sections.

The response body contains the following:

- The newly composed NSD
- The new set of translation rules

A more structured representation of the REST request and response can be found in Table 10.

Despite the fact that the ENC only manipulates NSD and translation rules, the input must also include the relevant VSB and list of CtxBs. In fact, the blueprints contain some information specific to the 5G EVE infrastructure that cannot be encoded directly in the NSD. More details about this are explained in the following sections.

Figure 4 shows the workflow of the interactions between the ENC and other components of the 5G EVE platform, by means of a message sequence diagram. The workflow is an extension of Figure 11 and Figure 12 in D4.1 [1], which show the procedure to for the definition and onboarding of a new ExpB. Here we resume from the phase called “Selection of CtxBs”, shown at the top of Figure 4. In this phase (omitted here for brevity), the experiment developer selects the contexts to be applied to a VSB. In the earlier release of the 5G EVE platform, the developer was also required to provide the NSD and the translation rules to enable the deployment of the new experiment. This would require a consistent amount of manual and error prone work for the experiment developer, since the NSD in ETSI NFV-IFA format is a quite complicated model. Now, the ENC enables the automatic composition of these two pieces of information, simplifying a lot the interaction of the user (in this case the experiment developer) with the 5G EVE platform.

Table 10: REST API for ENC

POST /experiments	
	JSON [23]
Request body	<pre> { "vsbRequest": { "vsBlueprint": {...}, "nsds": [{...}], "translationRules": [{...}], }, "contexts": [{ "ctxbRequest": { "ctxBlueprint": {...}, "nsds": [{...}], "translationRules": [{...}], }, "connectInput": { vl_1: ..., vl_2: ... } }, { ... }, { ... },] } </pre>
URI Variables	--
Query Parameters	--
Response body	<pre> { "expNsd": {...}, "translationRules": [{...}, {...}] } </pre>
Successful response HTTP code: 201 Accepted.	
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 422 Un-processable Entity, 500 INTERNAL ERROR.	

In Figure 4, after the completion of the selection of CtxBs by the experiment developer, the EBB starts preparing the input required by the ENC for the composition. The EBB retrieves the NSD and the Translation Rules related to the currently selected VSB from the Portal Catalogue (messages 1, 2). Then, it repeats the similar operation for each of the CtxBs selected in the previous phase of the workflow (messages 3 and 4 in the “loop” box). Now, the EBB has all the necessary information to contact the ENC and sends a request for a composition containing the input we discussed above in this section (message 5). As a response, it receives from the ENC a newly created NSD and the related Translation Rules. The EBB can now update the ExpB that it is building by associating the ENC output to it (message 7). Finally, the EBB shows some information describing the composition results to the experiment developer on the portal web interface (message 8). The workflow goes on with the “Definition of experiment details” phase. At the end of the procedure, the newly created ExpB, complete with all the information to be deployed and executed, is onboarded on the Portal Catalogue (phase “Experiment Blueprint Onboarding” in the workflow”). The last two phases are described in detail in D4.1 [1].

Figure 4: Composition request for and experiment NSD

4.2.2 Experiment NSD Composer algorithm

The ENC implements a procedure of composition that provides a trade-off between simplicity and customization. The experiment developer can easily create new versions of an experiment NSD just by applying new

contexts to their service templates. The algorithm grants safe, default decisions on how to perform the composition. That is possible thanks to the novel concept of Context Blueprint (CtxB), a template of one or more network elements describing an operational context for the network service. The CtxB defines experimental conditions for the service described in the VSB, like artificial background traffic or artificial traffic delay and it can include some parameters to customize its components.

Given the graph-like representation of the network service obtained by a VSB and shown in Figure 1, we defined two types of CtxB: PASS_THROUGH type and CONNECT type. The type also defines how to compose the context with the network topology of the VSB. The first type, PASS_THROUGH, indicates that the component is capable of applying some function or effect to the network traffic that passes through it. A common example is a component that applies artificial delay and/or artificial packet losses to the traffic received on an endpoint and resends it to another endpoint. The composition algorithm of the ENC inserts contexts of this type immediately after the RAN connection, in order to affect all the traffic going to service VNFs. In Figure 5 we can see the result of the composition for the network service in Figure 1 with a PASS_THROUGH context for delay generation.

Figure 5: Composition of a VSB with a CtxB of type PASS_THROUGH

The second type of CtxB, CONNECT, identifies a component or set of components that can apply an effect on the network service by simply being connected to it. A common example is an artificial traffic generator, which

can be used to create a situation of traffic congestion. We can assume that this context is made of two components, a source that generates the artificial traffic and a destination that receives it. The composition algorithm of the ENC inserts the two components by respectively connecting them to two different connectivity services. Figure 6 shows the result of the composition for the network service in Figure 1 with a CONNECT context for artificial traffic generation. Despite the example, the two components can also invert their source and destination roles allowing for the application of the context in both directions without the need to create a new topology.

Figure 6: Composition of a VSB with a CtxB of type CONNECT

The CtxB model described in D4.1 [1] has been extended to include the information about type. Since this is related to the EBB and determines the strategy for the composition, it has been named “compositionStrategy”. Table 3 in Section 2.2 reports the complete CtxB data model with the new field in italic.

Figure 7 shows the algorithm operation by means of a flowchart diagram. The flowchart focuses on the NSD composition and on elements for data-plane traffic. Indeed, the checks for input validation and error handling are not shown for the sake of simplicity.

When the ENC receives a request for the composition of a new experiment, it performs some preliminary input checks and triggers the composition algorithm (red box at the top of the flowchart). The algorithm makes a copy of the vertical service NSD, the one associated to the VSB, instantiating an experiment NSD. It also retrieves the Virtual Link (network) that provides RAN connectivity, labelled as RAN VL in the flowchart. Now, a loop starts to process each of the contexts to be composed with the experiment NSD. The algorithm retrieves the composition strategy to be used from the CtxB information and selects the corresponding list of operations (yellow diamond labelled as “Strategy?” in the flowchart). For strategy PASS_THROUGH, the context NSD

includes just one VNF to be added to the experiment NSD, in order to apply some effect to the traffic received by the vertical service. The VNF information is retrieved from the context NSD together with its connection points, which are needed to create the proper connections with other elements of the experiment. Moreover, a Virtual Link for data-plane traffic is retrieved from the context. This will be added to the service NSD as well. If the algorithm was able to retrieve all the previous information, it starts composing. The context VNF and Virtual Link are added to the experiment NSD. A connection is created between the new VNF and the Virtual Link for RAN access. Other connections in the experiment NSD are checked and fixed if necessary. Finally, the new experiment NSD is validated for correctness (bottom of the flowchart). The algorithm checks if another context is available in the input and restarts the composition procedure.

If the context's strategy is of type CONNECT, additional input can be provided for further customizing the composition. The algorithm checks for this in the step represented by the yellow diamond labelled as "Additional input?" in Figure 7. The provided input consists of the references to the Virtual Links, labelled VL1 and VL2 in the flowchart, to be used to connect the two VNFs coming from the context, labelled VNF1 and VNF2 in the flowchart. If the input is present, the algorithm safely tries to retrieve the two VLs from the experiment NSD. If they are not found, or if the input is not provided at all, the algorithm performs a safe default choice and it selects the RAN Virtual Link to connect VNF1 and a random data-plane Virtual Link to connect VNF2. After the preparation of all the elements needed for the composition, the two VNFs are added to the experiment NSD.

Figure 7: Flowchart of the ENC composition algorithm

Proper connections are created to attach VNF1 to VL1 and VNF2 to VL2 respectively. As for the PASS_THROUGH strategy, the new NSD is finally validated. If no more contexts are available in the input, the algorithm ends (red box at the bottom of the flowchart in Figure 7) and the ENC returns the output.

Since in 5G EVE there is the need to access VNFs for applying Day-2 configuration and for triggering the execution of tests, a management Virtual Link is provided in each NSD. All the VNFs composing a network service are connected to it via one of their connection points. The ETSI NFV-IFA 014 model is generic and does not provide options to distinguish between management elements and data-plane elements, so that this information is encoded in the blueprints. At the moment the identification of the VL for management is inferred by the `management` attribute in the items of the `endPoints` field of the VSB and CtxB. Examples of this can be found in Annex A and Annex E. In the next future the items in field `connectivityServices` (see Table 2) are going to be extended to include a field to directly flag them as management elements. Several checks in the algorithm make sure that the management network of the experiment network service is never used for the composition of data-plane components. Furthermore, new connections are added for components coming from contexts so that they have access to the management network.

The algorithm also needs to know where the RAN access is. The `ranConnection` attribute in the items of the `endPoints` field is used in both strategies to identify the VL with access to the RAN. In the PASS_THROUGH strategy the latter is used to attach a pass-through CtxB, in the CONNECT strategy it is used to connect the first VNF of the CtxB.

The algorithm flowchart does not mention deployment flavours and instantiation levels for the sake of simplicity. As discussed in Section 2.5, each combination of NsDF and NsLevel defines a variant of the service described by the NSD. The ENC composition algorithm can handle multiple NsDF and NsLevel and it is able to compose context's components with all the variants of the experiment network service.

After the NSD composition, the ENC algorithm generates a new set of Translation Rules. It takes the translation rules associated to the VSB and relevant NSD in input and generates a new set to be associated with the new ExpB and the newly created NSD. The input section of each translation rule is inherited untouched, since the VSB parameters are inherited by the ExpB during its construction with the EBB. The “`nsdId`”, “`nsFlavourId`”, and “`nsInstantiationLevelId`” are checked for correctness against the newly generated NSD and modified accordingly if necessary.

4.2.3 Implementation details

The ENC is implemented as a REST application using the Java programming language and the Spring framework [16]. Spring implements dependency injection and Inversion of Control, leveraging the developer from the dependency management between classes and from the task of instantiating and maintaining objects. Furthermore, Spring offers a huge ecosystem of extensions and third-party libraries to bootstrap any kind of applications in minutes. The developer can start focusing on business logic code almost immediately from the start of a new project.

Besides Spring, the ENC depends from some code of the portal catalogue for the Java implementation of blueprints and descriptors information models. The libraries containing Java classes for the VSB, ExpB, CtxB and their related components can be found in [17]. The libraries with the implementation of the ETSI NFV-IFA models for NSD and VNFD can be found in [18]. Not only the re-use of libraries is convenient but it also ensures the compatibility of the information models exchanged between the software components.

Finally, the ENC depends on JGraphT [19], a popular Java library to easily build graphs from your data and including many algorithms. The ENC uses JGraphT to create graph representations of network topologies defined by the NSD with the combination of a NsDf and a NsLevel. The graph is used to support the composition algorithm and for easily checking the results of the composition. Indeed, checking directly the NSD after a composition is not easy for a human and takes some time, while a graphical rendering of each topology in the form of a graph gives an instantaneous feedback on how the algorithm is working. JGraphT provides utility functions to export graphs for visualization in many formats. The ENC exports graphs in Graphviz format [20]. This tool has been used only for the debugging during the design and development of the ENC, but in the future, this feature could be also exposed to other components of 5G EVE via the REST API.

As shown in Figure 7, the algorithm to compose a service NSD with a list of contexts NSDs loops over the list of contexts and compose them one at a time with the service NSD. The type of the context, or composition strategy, defines the actions for the algorithm to follow. Anyway, the two procedures share some code, like input preparation, graph structures generation, logging, exception handling, and results validation. We apply a template method design pattern [21] to avoid code repetition between the two strategies and to make it easy to add new composition strategies in the future. Figure 8 shows a UML diagram of the main Java classes involved. For the sake of simplicity and clarity, only main classes and methods (sometimes without input parameters) are reported.

Figure 8: UML class diagram for the ENC. Main classes and methods only.

The ExperimentsController is the main access point to the application and it implements the methods to be triggered when a request arrives at the REST interface. The method composeExperiment is called when a POST request arrives on the path “/experiments”. Here, the input request is unpacked and some checks are performed to ensure the input is valid. Furthermore, the loop over the list of contexts is implemented. The ExperimentsController holds two association to NsdComposer with the two references `connectComposer` and `passThroughComposer`. Given the context’s strategy, the compose() method is invoked on the proper instance as shown in Figure 9.

```

for (Context ctx : request.getContexts()) {
    if (ctx.getStrategy() == CONNECT){
        connectComposer.compose(...);
    } else if (ctx.getStrategy() == PASSTHROUGH){
        passThroughComposer.compose(...);
    }
}

```

Figure 9: Section of "composeExperiment()" method. Simplified Java.

The NsdComposer abstract class is the base class of the Template method pattern. The “compose(...)” method implements common steps of the algorithm including logging, safe retrieval of some needed information from NSDs (both experiment and context), loop over the NsDF and NsLevel of the experiment NSD, graph building, NSD validation. At the right point in the algorithm operation a call is made to “composeWithStrategy(...)”, the abstract method declared in NsdComposer and implemented by ConnectComposer and PassThroughComposer. Figure 10 shows the simplified Java code of the NsdComposer class.

```

public abstract class NsdComposer {

    public void compose(...){

        // Common steps of the algorithm

        for (NsDf expNsDf: expNsd.getNsDf()) {
            for (NsLevel expNsLvl : expNsDf.getNsInstantiationLevel()) {

                // Common steps of the algorithm

                composeWithStrategy(...);

                // Common steps of the algorithm
            }
        }

        // Common steps of the algorithm

    }

    public abstract void composeWithStrategy(...);
}

```

Figure 10: NsdComposer class. Simplified Java.

ConnectComposer and PassThroughComposer classes are the variant part of the template method. They fill in the blank part of the composition algorithm with their own specific logic by implementing the abstract method “composeWithStrategy(...)”.

Figure 8 also show the NsdGraphService class that contains code related to building graphs from NSD and to exporting graphs for graphical rendering. NsdComposer is associated to this class and makes heavy use of it. As discussed above, given an NSD we can generate a network topology for each pair of distinct NsDF and NsLevel. To build a graph representation of the topology, VNF, VL and PNF profiles are mapped to different types of vertices, so to be rendered with different shapes and colours in the graphical export. By analysing the VNF and PNF connection points, edges are created to connect the corresponding vertices to the VL vertices. The external connectivity offered by the network service is defined through SAP declared in the SapD. SapD elements can be also considered connection points, but they can’t be mapped to graph edges since they would result in dangling edges (attached to only one vertex). Then, a SapD is mapped to another type of vertex. The “export(graph)” method of NsdGraphService generates a Graphviz text-based representation of the graph. Figure 11 shows a rendering example of a graph.

Figure 11: Graphviz rendering of a graph for a network topology.

As a final note, it’s important to make clear that the code snippets presented in this section do not include all the accessory code for the handling of exceptions and logging. Since the ESTI NFV-IFA models are quite complex, many checks are performed throughout the algorithm to ensure that models are always correct. More information on this in the next section. A debug mode of the algorithm is available; it prints all the operations to ease future development and the analysis of errors.

4.2.4 Model validation procedure

The ENC performs multiple checks to ensure that input, output, and temporary information models are valid.

The syntax check of the blueprints, NSD, Translation Rules, and related models is implemented thanks to the Java libraries mentioned in [17] and [18]. All the information elements are mapped to Plain Old Java Objects (POJOs) and their instance variables. Native Java data types are used when possible and custom types are created when needed. At execution time, the Spring framework uses Jackson [22] to serialize and deserialize the data models from and to the POJO implementation. The request body coming with a call to the REST API of

the ENC is deserialized from a JSON [23] or YAML [24] format to Java object instances. If the request schema does not comply with the model defined by the libraries, proper exceptions are raised. In the opposite way, the response body is generated by serializing the Java objects ensuring consistency in all the operations.

To check semantically the data models, each POJO provides a method called “isValid()”. Since the POJO representation of a blueprint, an NSD, and others is a tree-structured collection of Java objects, the method can be called recursively. “isValid()” checks for null values, inconsistent values in the model and so on. If something is wrong, the proper exception is raised.

The ENC performs many additional checks in the algorithm to ensure the validity of the NSD during the composition. For example, input validation is implemented to make sure that a blueprint, its related NSD and the Translation Rules contain coherent references to each other. Furthermore, consistency checks are performed on the NSD in addition to the ones provided by the “isValid()” method. As an example, we can consider the addition of a new VNF to the experiment NSD. To make the composition consistent, we need to add a reference to the VNFD identifier at the root level of the NSD, the VNF profile at the NsDF level, and finally a reference to the VNF profile at the NsLevel. Each one of these elements references the other and the algorithm makes sure that the references are correct. The same applies to Virtual Links. Also, the creation of connections between VNFs and VLs triggers a series of checks to always keep the model valid.

Finally, the graph representation of a network topology enables other kinds of validation. It has been already mentioned that creating a visual rendering of the network topology makes it easier to spot errors in the composition algorithm. The ENC is able to export graphs in Graphviz format, a text-based representation that can be rendered using one of the many open source implementations. The feature is actually targeted towards developers but it can also be exposed publicly to create visualizations in a web interface.

Apart from this manual check through visualization, we can verify the connectivity of the network topology programmatically. Indeed, each graph built from an NSD and a selection of its NsDF and NsLevel should be *connected*, meaning that it has at least one vertex and there is a path connecting each pair of vertices. JGraphT provides many common and well-known algorithms for graphs, among which we can find the ConnectivityInspector class, providing functions to check many connectivity aspects. The ENC uses this class to check that every topology defined in the service and experiment NSD is connected.

4.3 Translation into ETSI SOL001 descriptors

The process for onboarding blueprints for vertical services, execution contexts and experiments include the specification of the NSD defining how to deploy the instances of NFV Network Services (NS) where the experiment will be executed. As part of this onboarding phase, the experiment developer provides an NSD for each corresponding blueprint. Such NSD will include the declaration of all the possible deployment flavours and instantiation levels available for the given NS. The information model adopted for the NSD is based on the ETSI NFV IFA 014 specification [8], aligned with version 2.3.1, with some minor extensions to manage additional requirements for the NS deployment and its translation from the service blueprint concept. The high-level schema associated to the NSD components, based on the IFA 014 model, is depicted in Figure 12.

Figure 12: NSD overview (ETSI NFV IFA 014 format) [2]

The class diagram with the major information elements associated to an NSD is reported in Figure 13. The NSD includes lists of IDs for the descriptors of the included VNFs, PNFs and nested NSs. The *NsVirtualLinkDesc* represent the descriptors of the virtual links defining how these VNFs, PNFs and NSs should be interconnected, while the “paths” should be followed by the traffic flows crossing the various service functions are described through the *Vnffg* (VNF forwarding graph) elements. As already stated in previous sections, the external connectivity offered by the network service is defined through service access points declared in the *SapD*, whereas the information about the “dimension” of the network service (i.e. number and size of the VMs where the VNFs run, bandwidth and QoS parameters of the virtual links, etc.) is encoded through the *NsDeploymentFlavour* and the *NsLevel* information elements. Their combination provides the set of “size options” available to deploy a meaningful and working network service. The specific pair of deployment flavour and instantiation level needs to be specified at the onboarding.

Figure 13: NSD class diagram

When the blueprint and the corresponding IFA 014-based NSD are onboarded at the 5G EVE Portal Catalogue, the NSD is also transferred at the InterWorking Framework (IWF) Catalogue. Here it will be processed by the Multi-Site Network Orchestrator (MSO) when deploying the inter-site network services. Since the North-Bound Interface (NBI) exposed by the 5G EVE IWF is based on the ETSI NFV SOL 005 interface [15], the IWL Catalogue accepts the onboarding of NSDs in the format specified by the ETSI NFV SOL 001 specification [10]. In this format, the NSDs are defined using the TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications) Simple Profile in YAML [11]. During the onboarding phase, the 5G EVE Portal Catalogue will thus need to translate the NSDs between the ETSI NFV IFA 014 format and the ETSI NFV SOL 001 format. This translation is performed by the IWF driver, as shown in Figure 14.

Following the NFV SOL 001 format, a NSD is a deployment template that refers to VNF descriptors (VNFDs), PNF descriptors (PNFDs) and nested NSDs and includes Virtual Link descriptors (VLDs) and VNF Forwarding Graph descriptors (VNFFGD). This approach is exactly the same one adopted in the NFV IFA 014 format. However, “deployment flavours” from ETSI NFV IFA 014 model are supported in the TOSCA template as lower level service templates in the NSD file structure, while the concept of “instantiation levels” from ETSI NFV IFA 014 is not supported at all in the latest NFV SOL 001 specification. For this reason, each IFA 014-compliant NSD is translated into multiple SOL 001-compliant NSDs, one for each possible combination of <deployment flavour; instantiation level> available in the original NSD.

Figure 14: Onboarding procedure and IFA 014 to SOL 001 translation

The mapping of the other NSD parameters follows the guidelines specified in the ETSI NFV SOL 001 specification [10] about the mapping between IFA 014 information model and TOSCA concepts and reported in Table 11 for completeness.

Table 11: Mapping between ETSI GS NFV IFA 014 information model and TOSCA concepts

ETSI GS NFV IFA 014 information element	TOSCA concept
NSD	TOSCA service template
SapD	Node template with type <code>tosca.nodes.nfv.Sap</code>
MonitoredData	Policy with type <code>tosca.policies.nfv.NsMonitoring</code>
LifeCycleManagementScript	Interface with type <code>Nslcm</code> Scripts in the NS package
VnfProfile	Property of VNF node template with data type <code>tosca.datatypes.nfv.VnfProfile</code>
VirtualLinkProfile	Property of <code>NsVirtualLink</code> node template with data type <code>tosca.datatypes.nfv.VIProfile</code>
NsProfile	Property of NS node template with data type <code>tosca.datatypes.nfv.NsProfile</code>
AffinityOrAntiAffinityGroup	Policy with type <code>tosca.policies.nfv.NsAffinityRule</code> or <code>tosca.policies.nfv.NsAntiAffinityRule</code>
Dependencies	Dependency requirements
Vnffgd	Group with type <code>tosca.groups.nfv.VNFFG</code>
Nfspd	Node template with type <code>tosca.nodes.nfv.NFP</code>
NsVirtualLinkDesc	Node template with type <code>tosca.nodes.nfv.NsVirtualLink</code>
NsVirtualLinkConnectivity	Requirement and capability between <code>PnfExtCp</code> or <code>VnfExtCp</code> and <code>NsVirtualLink</code> node templates
VirtualLinkDf	Properties of the <code>NsVIProfile</code> data type
Pnfd	TOSCA service template
PnfExtCpd	Node template with type <code>tosca.nodes.nfv.PnfExtCp</code>

In terms of software, the IWF driver that performs the IFA to SOL translation is implemented in Java and imports two libraries, released as open source software under the Apache 2.0 license. These libraries implement these two reference information models:

- IFA NSD information model library, available on Github at https://github.com/nextworks-it/nfv-ifa-libs/tree/feat-librefactor/NFV_MANO_LIBS_DESCRIPTOR
- SOL 001 information model library, available on Github at https://github.com/nextworks-it/nfv-sol-libs/tree/master/NFV_MANO_SOL001_LIBS_DESCRIPTOR

The IWF driver is implemented as a particular NFV orchestrator (NFVO) catalogue driver, imported and loaded in the 5G EVE Portal Catalogue. The NFVO drivers project is a software component also released as open source software under the Apache 2.0 license and available on Github at <https://github.com/nextworks-it/nfvo-drivers>. The specific SOL 001 driver is available in the folder https://github.com/nextworks-it/nfvo-drivers/tree/master/NFVO_CATALOGUE_SPECIFIC_DRIVERS/src/main/java/it/nextworks/nfvmano/nfvdriver/sol.

Annex B shows an example of an NSD in NFV-IFA 014 format and Annex C shows its translation to the NFV-SOL 001 format.

4.4 Generation of data collection streams

The generation of data collection streams is the process relating to the acquisition of monitoring information defined in the corresponding blueprints (i.e. VSB and CtxBs for application metrics and ExpB for both infrastructure metrics and KPIs) to correctly configure the 5G EVE end-to-end Monitoring Platform, based on the joint operation of both the Data Collection Manager (DCM) from the IWF [12], which is the central component of the multi-broker, publish-subscribe messaging queuing architecture that is used for delivering and saving all the monitoring data generated for a given experiment, and the Experiment monitoring and Maintenance & Results Collection toolchain from the 5G EVE Portal [1][2], in charge of performing a set of specific operations to the monitoring data received from the DCM (e.g. data collection, aggregation, pre-processing, indexing and storage) and visualize it in an online fashion.

4.4.1 Blueprints' data model

The monitoring information is extracted by the ELM component [1][2] from the blueprints described in Section 2, generating the useful data to feed the DCM. As commented before, these blueprints are the VSB, CtxBs and ExpB.

The information that can be extracted from these blueprints for monitoring purposes are the following:

- **Vertical Service and Context Blueprints:** application metrics are defined in both blueprints, being included in a list with the *applicationMetrics* field. The parameters that can be defined for each application metric, already presented in D4.1 [1], can be also found in the examples provided in Annex A and Annex E, related to a VSB and CtxB example respectively. In short, the *metricId* parameter is used by the ELM to generate the topic name, as showed in Section 4.4.2. Other parameters that are useful for the configuration of the dashboards in the Data Collection and Storage (DCS) are, for example, the *metricCollectionType* and the *unit*.
- **Experiment Blueprints:** following the same philosophy as the previous case, a list of infrastructure metrics and KPIs can be found in this type of blueprints, tagged with the fields called *metrics* and *kpis*, respectively. Moreover, the VSB and CtxBs are identified with the fields *vsBlueprintId* and *ctxBlueprintIds*, respectively, being used for obtaining the application metrics as commented in the previous point. The parameters defined in the ExpB, already presented in D4.1 [1], can be also found in a specific example provided in Annex G. As a result, the IDs provided for each case (*metricId* and *kpiId*) are also used to generate the topic name, and again, parameters such as the *unit* or the *metricCollectionType* (in the case of infrastructure metrics) can be used for correctly configuring the monitoring dashboards to be presented in the Portal.

4.4.2 Topic name composition

Mainly, the transformation performed by the ELM is the composition of the topic name to be used for delivering through the Monitoring platform the data related to each infrastructure metric, application metric and KPI, and

whose format has been already defined in deliverable D3.3 [13] in the topic framework proposal, but it is also included here for the sake of completeness⁴.

Then, for data topics, which are the ones that are generated by the ELM, the current format to be followed is the following: `<exp>.<site>.[application_metric|infrastructure_metric|kpi].<value>`, where:

- `<exp>`: is the experiment ID, uniquely identifying the experiment itself. This value is generated and assigned by the ELM.
- `<site>`: identifies the site facility where the data is extracted (e.g. Spain, Italy, etc.). This comes from the field called *compatibleSites* in VSB (Table 2) and CtxBs (Table 3) and the field called *sites* in ExpB (Table 4).
- `[application_metric|infrastructure_metric|kpi]`: it is a key word that indicates the type of information to which belongs the next parameter. In particular, from VSB and CtxBs (Table 2 and Table 3, respectively), application metrics are obtained from *applicationMetrics* field, so these metrics will be tagged as *application_metric*. In ExpB (Table 4), *infrastructure_metric* tag comes from the metrics included in *metrics* field, and *kpi* tag is used for the KPIs that comes from *kpis* field.
- `<value>`: set the name of the parameter to be monitored (e.g. latency), identifying the metric/KPI. In VSB and CtxBs (Table 2 and Table 3, respectively), application metrics are obtained from *applicationMetrics* field, using the *metricId* subfield to define the required `<value>`. In ExpB (Table 4), metrics are included in *metrics* field and `<value>` is defined using the *metricId* subfield, and the same for KPIs, which are defined in *kpis* field and `<value>` is defined using the *kpiId* subfield.

Furthermore, this is a preliminary definition of the topic name, and it is expected to make some small changes on it related to the introduction of more useful information, such as the specific use case related to the metric or KPI. These updates will be included in the upcoming deliverable D3.4 [35].

4.4.3 Distribution of monitoring data

All the monitoring data that is needed by the 5G EVE Monitoring platform for its configuration is provided by the ELM, sending all this information by using the *publish* operation exposed by the DCM API, as presented in deliverable D4.2 [2], where it can be also found the information model that applies to the data to be sent.

The monitoring data does not only include the topic name, but also all the parameters related to each metric and KPI without any transformation⁵, just to forward it to the DCS (subcomponent of the Experiment monitoring and Maintenance & Results Collection toolchain) [2], which will use these parameters to generate the dashboards that will be presented through the Data Visualization component [2] from the Portal.

In this way, the DCM provides this operation through a REST API, allowing other components from the 5G EVE platform (mainly, the ELM) to publish data into the publish-subscribe queue without needing to implement a specific plugin or library related to implementation issues. The endpoint is `POST /dcm/publish/<topicName>`, where `<topicName>` is the topic in which the component that is sending the information wants to publish it. In the case of the ELM, it will publish the information related to the application metrics, infrastructure metrics and KPIs in the so-called signalling topics, already presented in D3.3 [12], and which are used for triggering the topic subscription or the withdrawal processes in the DCM. The signalling topics defined⁶ by the DCM are:

- `signalling.metric.application`: signalling topic for application metric's data.
- `signalling.metric.infrastructure`: signalling topic for infrastructure metric's data.

⁴ Note that there are some modifications comparing to the specification provided in D3.3 [12]. For example, in D3.3, there are no distinction between infrastructure and application metrics, aspect that is included in this case and that will also be included in the next D3.4. Furthermore, *result* field is not included here as monitoring data, as it is not included currently as information in the blueprints, still being under discussion within WP5 scope.

⁵ This information can be found in D4.1 [1], chapters 5.2.4 Metrics and 5.2.5 KPI.

⁶ Again, the signalling topics presented in this deliverable have been updated from the definition provided in the deliverable D3.3, as now *metrics* can be either *application* or *infrastructure metrics*, and also *results* are not being considered now.

- *signalling.kpi*: signalling topic for KPI's data.

The request body must be formatted in JSON [23], being composed by only one parameter called *records*, which is a list of elements called *values*. Each *value* contains the following parameters:

- *topic*: the topic name generated by the ELM.
- *expId*: the *expId* of the experiment that is going to be executed, also generated and provided by the ELM.
- *action*: can be either “subscribe” or “unsubscribe”, depending on the phase in which this operation is executed.
- *context*⁷: this includes all the parameters related to each application metric, infrastructure metric or KPI extracted directly from the blueprints (e.g. ID, name, collection type, unit, interval, etc.), in order to be used by the DCS for generating the monitoring dashboards. In the case of both application and infrastructure metrics, all the parameters included in blueprints are copied in this field, but in the case of KPIs, the *formula* and *metricIds* fields are omitted, as they are not useful for the process that generates the dashboards.

A specific example that reflects the data sent from the ELM to the DCM through this *publish* operation can be found in Annex J. This is also summarized in the diagram shown in Figure 15, also including the acquisition of all the data required for building the topic name, based on the procedure described in all subchapters of Section 4.4.

⁷ This parameter is defined for the first time in this deliverable, and will be extended in next D4.5.

Figure 15: Generation of data sent from ELM to DCM, obtained from blueprints.

Finally, the DCM performs several operations after receiving this data from the ELM, which are basically the following ones:

- Create or delete the topic in the publish-subscribe platform (depending on the *action* field), sending also a notification to the DCS in order to enable or disable the consumers that receives the monitoring data in that topic. This operation is fully described in D3.3 [12] and will be updated in D3.4 [35] with the final specification.
- Send the *context* information to the DCS, in order to generate the monitoring dashboards. This operation will be fully described in the next D4.5 [33].

4.5 Generation of configuration for experiment execution

As shown in Figure 2, there are three processes that take part in the configuration and execution of an experiment. One is the preparation of the data collection mechanisms, operation governed by ELM, which is detailed in section 4.4. The other two, governed by the EEM, are:

- Day-2 configuration;
- Test case execution.

Figure 16 below represents the participating modules in both procedures. The starting point is an experiment already deployed on top of the infrastructure of one or several sites. This instantiation is triggered by the MSO and executed by the local NFVOs, which are not depicted for simplification. Only after a correct deployment of a NS can the experiment be executed.

Figure 16: Components involved in Day-2 configuration and Test case execution.

Right after deployment, the experiment execution starts at the ELM, which triggers an experiment execution job at the EEM, and shares with it the required parameters. Many of these will be extracted from the Experiment Blueprints/Descriptors, in particular from the Test Case Blueprints/Descriptors (their IDs are included in the ExpB/ExpD, as commented in sections 2.3 and 2.4, respectively). Others, concretely those that are only available after instantiation (e.g. IP addresses of the VNFs/PNFs), will have to be provided by the Multi-Site NSO (coming from the NFVOs), and are not scope of this Deliverable (therefore the black dotted line in Figure 16 going from the MSO to the EEM). More information about this can be found in Section 3.2.3 of deliverable D4.1 [1] and Section 3.3 of deliverable D3.3 [12].

In the EEM the approach is the same for both processes day-2 configuration and test case execution: a Robot Framework [27] script is launched via Jenkins [26] to handle the required tasks and interact with the Runtime Configurator (RC). At this stage of the project, the EEM creates an SSH connection with the RC and triggers an Ansible [25] script which in turn interacts with the site(s) VNFs/PNFs. In future versions, a REST API will be developed to substitute the SSH connection. All the details about workflows and interface definitions between ELM, EEM and RC are included in Deliverable D5.2 [7], while in the present document we will concentrate on the subsequent transformations done in each of the steps.

Finally, the interaction between RC and the different VNFs/PNFs is also depicted using a dotted line; this specification can be found in Deliverable D3.3 [12].

4.5.1 Blueprints' data model

As commented above, there are several sources of information for the EEM to obtain parameters that are required to trigger either the day-2 configuration or the experiment execution tasks; this is shown in Figure 17. We have already mentioned that EEM obtains instantiation-based parameters from the MSO, mainly IP addresses both in the management and in the data planes of the deployed VNFs/PNFs. The other sources are:

- The RC: before starting any day-2 configuration or test execution operation in the RC, the EEM notifies the RC that it wants to trigger any of these operations, receiving back an ID (Config_ID or TC_Exec_ID, depending on the type of operation). This permits the status control of the different operations by the EEM.
- The ELM: the information that can be extracted from the Test Case Blueprints is either user-related (e.g. parameters like initial bandwidth and modification pattern in case we want to generate traffic) or

infrastructure-related (e.g. information about physical interfaces). The user-related information is incorporated into the blueprints and descriptors directly by the experimenters using the 5G EVE Portal.

- The EEM itself, which can store fixed variables like the management IP address of the RC or the Kafka [28] bus, or the location of the different scripts that are available (at the RC or at any external catalogue).

Figure 17: Sources of information for the EEM.

The TcB information model is discussed in Section 2.5. A TcB example in YAML can be found in Annex F.

4.5.2 Robot Framework “building blocks”

Experiment developers willing to execute tests on top of 5G EVE infrastructure will have to generate scripts both for day-2 configuration [32] and for the execution of experiments. There are many possibilities for this, but the project is generating some “building blocks” which will be possible to reuse, in an attempt to simplify some of these scripts. In particular, in the short term we are generating both the Robot Framework and the Ansible scripts for simple tools like Ping (delay measurement), Iperf [29] (traffic generation) and TC [31] (packet loss or delay generation), for experiment execution, and Beats [30] (data shipper), for day-2 configuration. The detailed description of how the metrics and KPIs are evaluated over the collected data is provided in D5.2 [7] and the further explained in upcoming D5.3 [34].

We can use these examples to show, on the first hand, the mapping of user/infrastructure parameters at the Test Case Blueprint, and in following sections, their associated transformations.

- Ping test case:

The Ping tool command has the following format:

```
ping [ -LRUbdfnqrvVaAB] [ -c count] [ -i interval] [ -l preload] [ -p
pattern] [ -s packetsize] [ -t ttl] [ -w deadline] [ -F flowlabel] [
-I interface] [ -M hint] [ -Q tos] [ -S sndbuf] [ -T timestamp option]
[ -W timeout] [ hop ...] destination
```

Choosing for example a few parameters which could be relevant to measure the delay between two endpoints, we would have:

- `-c count`: stop after sending count ECHO_REQUEST packets (default 4 or 5, depending on Operating System)
- `-i interval`: wait interval seconds between sending each packet (default 1second).
- `-s packetsize`: specifies the number of data bytes to be sent (default is 56B, which translates into 64 ICMP data bytes when combined with header data).

This sort of parameters would be user-related parameters, as we would permit experimenters to define them. Alternatively, the destination IP address could be an infrastructure-related parameter, if we have a fixed probe towards which we can send the ICMP ECHOS. It could also be a parameter coming from the Multi-Site NSO, in case the ping probes were deployed as part of the test case network service.

b) Iperf test case:

Following the same reasoning as above, Iperf could be launched using the following simplified format:

```
iperf [-s|-c host] [options]
```

This case has the particularity that both a client and a server must be configured, but user parameters could be:

- -u, --udp: use UDP rather than TCP
- -w, --window n[KM]: determines TCP window size (socket buffer size)
- -b, --bandwidth n[KM]: set target bandwidth to n bits/sec (default 1 Mbit/sec). This setting requires UDP (-u).

Instead, infrastructure parameters could be the management addresses of both the client and server modules.

c) Traffic Control test case:

Two network impairments can be emulated using Linux TC: delay and packet loss. To add a constant delay to an interface, we could execute something like:

```
tc qdisc add dev <dev> root netem delay <delay>, where
```

- <dev> identifies the interface where the rules will be applied
- <delay> is the delay in milliseconds to be introduced

Similarly, to emulate packet loss:

```
tc qdisc add dev <dev> root netem loss <loss>, where
```

- <loss> is the percentage of packet loss to be introduced

Both the delay and the packet loss parameters would be user-defined, while the interface ID could probably be an infrastructure parameter (or be provided by the Multi-Site NSO).

d) Beats day-2 configuration:

This procedure is complex, but suffice to say that the most critical parameter is the Kafka topic that the activated data shipper must use to publish monitoring data in the Kafka bus. This, of course, is not a user-dependant parameter, but is created by the ELM and passed as an infrastructure parameter. In fact, there are no `userParameters` in this call, which serves to show that user and infrastructure parameters can be required or not depending on the specific use case.

4.5.3 Transformations between Experiment Lifecycle Manager and Experiment Execution Manager

As already stated, workflows and APIs for this process are included in Deliverable D5.2 [7]. In particular, the API between the two modules defines the triggering of an experiment execution request⁸ as shown in Table 12.

⁸ The request for a day-2 configuration request would be very similar. For example, instead of “executionId”, we would have “configurationId”. But with regards to this exercise, the mapping of parameters in the `testCaseDescriptorConfiguration` would be equivalent.

Table 12: Experiment Execution Request data type

Name	Type
executionId*	String
experimentDescriptorId*	String
nsInstanceId*	String
testCaseDescriptorConfiguration	Map<String, Map<String, String>>

* Mandatory fields.

The transformation of parameters between the ELM and the EEM is therefore immediate (via this API) if we consider all the blocks:

1. The TcB fields storing user parameters are completed by the experimenter via the Portal, deriving in a Test Case Descriptor (see [7]) in which both user and infrastructure parameters are present.
2. All those parameters of the Test Case Descriptor are encoded into the `testCaseDescriptorConfiguration` field of the ELM/EEM API.
3. The EEM translates those parameters received from the API in Robot Framework variables.

Using the examples of the building blocks for test execution (ping, iperf and tc) from above, the `testCaseDescriptorConfiguration` field in the API could look like this:

```
Map<ping, destination, Map<count, c_value>, Map<interval, i_value>,
Map<packetsize, s_value>>
Map<iperf, -s, Map<protocol, u_value>>
Map<tc, interface, Map<delay, delay_ms>>
Map<tc, interface, Map<loss, loss_percentage>>
```

And these would be translated into Robot Framework variables that could be (for the ping case only):

```
#{DST_PROBE_DP_ADDRESS} == destination
#{NUMBER_PACKETS} == c_value
#{INTERVAL} == i_value
#{PACKET_SIZE} == s_value
```

4.5.4 Transformations between Experiment Execution Manager and Runtime Configurator

Although these are not WP4 modules, we include a short comment on this transformation for the sake of completeness. As stated above in the introduction of Section 4.5, the EEM establishes an SSH session towards the RC, and triggers the execution of an Ansible script. An example of command for the ping use case could be:

```
ansible-playbook -i hosts measureDelay.yml -e
"dst_server_ip=#{DST_PROBE_DP_ADDRESS} packets=#{NUMBER_PACKETS}
interval=#{INTERVAL} size=#{PACKET_SIZE}"
```

As seen, the transformation in this step is from Robot Framework variables to Ansible parameters, listed after the “-e” tag. The command above would trigger the “measureDelay” playbook, with credentials listed in the file “hosts” and parameters as defined by the original user or infrastructure parameters of the test case blueprint.

Similarly, for a day-2 configuration call, the command could be:

```
ansible-playbook -i hosts measureDelayConfig.yml -e
"kafka_topic=#{KAFKA_TOPIC}"
```

We can see how the Kafka topic that was mentioned in Section 4.5.2 as an infrastructure parameter is also the main parameter to be passed to the RC.

4.6 Software licenses

In Table 13 we report the licenses of the main software tools developed or used in the activity of Task 4.3. Most of them are GPLv2, which is pretty adapted to usage in the industry. Indeed, it is possible to copy, distribute and modify the software as long as the developer track changes/dates in source files. In addition, any modifications to or software including (via compiler) GPL-licensed code must also be made available under the GPL along with build & install instructions. Others are licensed under Apache 2.0, which is the most appreciated one since this license makes sure that the user does not have to worry about infringing any patents by using the software. The user is granted a license to any patent that covers the software.

Table 13: Software licenses

Component	License
Experiment Blueprint Builder	Apache License 2.0
Experiment NSD Composer	Apache License 2.0
Portal Catalogue	Apache License 2.0
IFA NSD information model library	Apache License 2.0
SOL 001 information model library	Apache License 2.0
SOL 001 specific driver under the NFVO driver	Apache License 2.0
Experiment Lifecycle Manager	Apache License 2.0
Experiment Execution Manager	Apache License 2.0
JGraphT	Eclipse Public License - v 2.0 GNU LESSER GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE v2.1
Spring Framework	Apache License 2.0
Graphviz	Eclipse Public License – v 1.0
FasterXML Jackson	Apache License 2.0
Ansible	GNU General Public License v3.0
Robot Framework	Apache License 2.0
Jenkins	MIT License
Elastic Stack Beats	Apache License 2.0 Elastic License

5 Example of the overall transformation for a specific use case

The Transport Tracker use case introduced in Section 3.1 is used in this section to present a detailed example of all the model transformations. The example is organized in the experiment phases presented in deliverable D4.1 [1]. We assume that all the VSB, CtxB, and relevant NSDs are already onboarded on the Portal Catalogue.

During the experiment design and definition phase, the EBB presents to the experiment developer a series of guided steps towards building and onboarding the ExpB. Figure 18 shows a screenshot of the relevant part of the Portal GUI. The numbered steps have been superposed to the original snapshot in order to support the discussion of the example. The full set of images is available in D4.2 [2].

Figure 18: EBB building steps taken from 5G EVE Portal GUI.

Step 1

In Step 1, the experiment developer can fill in the id, name, version and description for the new ExpB to be created. In our example, the experiment developer inserts the following information:

- Id: “expb_ares2t_tracker”
- Name: “Ares2T Tracking Experiment”
- Version: “1.0”
- Description: “Ares2T tracking service with artificial delay and background traffic”

Step 2

In Step 2, the experiment developer can select the trial site of choice within the 5G EVE Platform for actual experiment execution. For the purpose of our example, he/she selects the Italian 5G EVE site facility hosted by TIM in Turin. Then, the EBB displays the list of available VSBs in the Portal Catalogue and the experiment developer selects the one with ID “vsb_ares2t_tracker”, reported in YAML format in Annex A. The EBB also retrieves the NSD and Translation Rules associated with the selected VSB.

Step 3

In Step 3, a list of available and compatible CtxBs is presented to the experiment developer. In our example, the experiment developer wants to test the service under the condition of delayed traffic and under the presence of additional background traffic on the virtual links composing the service network. He selects the CtxB with ID “Netem_Delay_Generator” and the CtxB with ID “ctx_bg_traffic” (Annex E). As done for the VSB, the EBB retrieves from the Portal Catalogue the necessary NSDs and Translation Rules. At this moment, the EBB interacts with the ENC to request the composition of the elements selected by the experiment developer, as shown in the workflow from Figure 4.

The ENC analyses the vertical service NSD and uses it as the source for creating an experiment NSD. The NSD for the Transport Tracker use case has one NsDF and two NsLevel, named “small” and “big”. Such two levels share the same topology but one VNF is smaller or bigger in terms of computing resources. We are going to use

only the “big” instantiation level in this section without loss of generality. Before starting the composition, the topology of the NSD is the one shown in Figure 11. The ENC composes one context at a time with the experiment NSD. It starts with the “Netem_Delay_Generator”, a context of type “PASS_THROUGH”. The relevant composition strategy is used and a new version of the NSD is generated. A graphical representation of the new topology, for the NsLevel “big” is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Composition of the Transport Tracker service with a delay generator context.

The green block named “vnfp_netem” is the VNF profile added to the NSD. The algorithm places it immediately after the SAP with RAN access, from which the user traffic flows towards the service. A new VL is also added, called “vlp_vl_dg_out”, in the lower part of the image. After the composition, all the VMs enjoy a well-established connection to the VL for management traffic, “vlp_vl_tracking_mgt”, in the upper left corner of the image.

The ENC now selects the second CtxB, “ctx_bg_traffic”. The second context is of type “CONNECT” and requires the second strategy to be correctly composed. The composition is applied incrementally on the experiment NSD generated previously. Figure 20 shows a graphical representation of the new topology for the NsLevel “big”. The composition algorithm adds two new VNF profiles here, “bg_traffic_src” and “bg_traffic_dst”, and it handles the proper connections for management and data traffic.

It can be seen how the graph complexity grows even with only two contexts being applied. Thus, writing the NSD of the experiment manually would be a hard, time-consuming, and error-prone process. The ENC prevents that problem from happening with the proposed approach, making this operation automatic.

Step 4

In Step 4 of the procedure shown in Figure 18, the EBB receives the output from the ENC (experiment NSD and Translation Rules) and onboards it to the Portal Catalogue.

Step 5

In Step 5, the Translation Rules are shown to the user for further customization. For the ExpB in our example, we keep untouched the Translation Rules of the VSB as shown in Annex D. The ENC takes care of updating the IDs of NSD, NsDF, and NsLevel, according to the NSD generated by the composition.

Step 6

In Step 6, the experiment developer completes the ExpB with pertaining information of involved metrics and

KPIs. In our example, the experiment developer selects to measure CPU and memory consumption of the VNFs involved in the experiment. Furthermore, the experiment developer defines two KPIs, one for assessing the response time of the Tracker Service and one for the memory consumption.

Step 7

In Step 7, the experiment developer selects the desired Test Case Blueprint containing the code to run the experiment.

Annex G shows the final ExpB generated by the EBB. Please notice the “metrics” and “kpis” sections. The TcBs are referenced here with their IDs in section “tcBlueprintIds” of the YAML file. The ExpB also keeps track of the VSB it was built from (“vsBlueprintId”) and the CtxBs used for the composition (“ctxBlueprintIds”).

Figure 20: Composition of the Transport Tracker service with both a delay generator and a background traffic contexts.

Once the Experiment Design and Definition phase is concluded, the new ExpB is onboarded to the Portal Catalogue with the procedure described in deliverable D4.1, Section 3.2.1.3 [1]. The ExpB is now available for the Experimenter.

In the experiment preparation phase, the vertical experimenter selects the newly created ExpB through the Portal GUI. He also sets up values for the parameters of the service, in our example the expected number of tracked devices as shown in Annex A, section “parameters” of the VSB. The 5G EVE platform will use the Translation Rules to select the NsLevel based on this value. The vertical experimenter also sets up the parameters for the contexts, as the amount of delay and background traffic, and the parameters for the TcB. From this procedure, the Portal GUI generates an ExpD, linked to the ExpB and containing the parameter values (see Annex H). The vertical experimenter now sends a scheduling request for the experiment execution through the Portal GUI, so that the site owner prepares the environment of the experiment. More details on this in deliverable D4.1, Section 3.2.2.2 and 3.2.2.3 [1].

At the time defined by the scheduling request, it starts the experiment execution phase, where the experiment is instantiated and properly configured⁹ for the execution of both Day-2 configuration and experiment test cases¹⁰. During the experiment instantiation, as commented in D3.3, Annex A.3 [12], the topics are provisioned from the ELM to the DCM through the signalling topics, as presented in Section 4.4.3. Annex J shows the requests sent by the ELM for this specific use case, according to the blueprints already mentioned. Then, when the monitoring platform is correctly configured and the experiment is ready to start, the experiment status changes to configuring, performing the Day-2 configuration required for the experiment. After this, the experiment enters in the running status, executing the different test cases defined for it. During this process, both application and infrastructure metrics defined for this use case are collected from the monitored components and published in the publish-subscribe monitoring system, then being pushed to the DCM, which will deliver the metrics values to the subscribed components consequently (i.e. the DCS and the KPI calculation and validation components). The metrics and KPIs can be monitored through the Data Visualization model from the 5G EVE Portal, using the dashboards configured with the information extracted from the blueprints, as commented in Section 4.4.3. This process lasts until the experiment is finished, moment in which the results of the experiment are presented.

Finally, with regards to experiment execution, it can be seen that the example of TcB provided in Annex F is very similar to the discussion in section 4.5 for the TC use case. The blueprint for this example experiment enhances a little bit the options for the experimenter (it includes the possibility to determine also the delay variance and a dependency percentage between consecutive delay values), but the philosophy is totally equivalent: the user and/or infrastructure parameters of the TcB (input to ELM) will end up, in the more general case, being transformed into Robot Framework variables (at the EEM).

In particular, there are three `userParameters` and two `infrastructureParameters` in the TcB of the Annex, which would translate into variables that could look like those in section 4.5:

- `{DELAY} == $$var$.delay`
- `{VARIANCE} == $$var$.delay_var`
- `{DEPENDENCY} == $$var$.dep`
- `{INPUT_INTERFACE} == '$$varX'`
- `{OUTPUT_INTERFACE} == '$$varY'`

It has to be noted that the script in the TcB of Annex F is not a Robot Framework script. This is possible of course for experiment developers, who can develop their own scripts (for day-2 configuration and even for experiment execution) in the language that they prefer. However, this demands a much more detailed knowledge of the underlying infrastructure and capabilities. Therefore, it will be recommended, unless the VNF providers provide both target VNFs (those that need to be tested) and testing VNFs (i.e., the testing tools), and these include the appropriate mechanisms to interact with the monitoring mechanisms of 5G EVE, that they take advantage of the building blocks that 5G EVE will provide and provide their scripts in Robot Framework.

⁹ More details on this in deliverable D4.1, Section 3.2.3.1 and 3.2.3.2 [1].

¹⁰ More details on this in deliverable D3.3, Annex B.3 [12].

6 Conclusion

This deliverable has introduced and formalized the concept of model transformation operations that take place within the 5G EVE Portal. Such operations allow exposing high-level, abstract models to vertical stakeholders, which need to be adapted into lower layer, platform specific configurations and actionable items. This document has presented the details on how that transformation process happens, starting from the high-level templates known as blueprints to the descriptors and configuration files to be fed into the components of the InterWorking Framework, including both the Multi-site Service Orchestrator and the Runtime Configurator. In this regard, this document fills the gaps introduced in D4.1 and D4.2, in which a number of workflows and interfaces had been presented, but some of the more complex operations carried out by Portal components were still defined at the functional level only. In addition, it also specifies how the information provided by the vertical in the blueprint are translated by means of automated tools into configurations to be pushed to the IWF, by limiting the human intervention and thus making the usage of the 5G EVE experimentation facilities much simpler and less error prone. In order to improve the understanding of the proposed approach, the Transport Tracker use case developed by the vertical Ares2T internal to the 5G EVE project was used as a running example case to which make reference in the description of tools. For that purpose, a number of annexes were also provided at the end of the document showing concrete examples of how the software operates on data models, and which are the inputs and outputs in a real use case.

Some of the presented tools are still under development and integration in the 5G EVE Portal at the moment of writing this document, and the plan is that all of them should be included in the next software release expected at month 24 (June 2020), including a complete integration among all components inside the Portal backend and the integration between these components and those provided by other work packages in the 5G EVE project.

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Annex A – VSB example

VSB for Ares2T tracking service use-case:

```
# vsb_ares2t_tracker.yaml
---
blueprintId: 'vsb_ares2t_tracker'
version: '1.0'
name: ARES2T Tracker service
description: Blueprint for 5G EVE Tracker service using 5G network to collect
mobility
  data user devices.
parameters:
  - parameterId: number_of_tracked_devices
    parameterName: Number of tracked devices
    parameterType: number
    parameterDescription: Number of devices equipped with the 5G EVE Tracking
  I Service(Mandatory)
    applicabilityField: Smart transport
atomicComponents:
  - componentId: tracker_backend
    serversNumber: 1
    endPointsIds:
      - cp_tracker_ext_in
      - cp_tracker_data
      - cp_tracker_mgt
  - componentId: visualization_tool
    serversNumber: 1
    endPointsIds:
      - cp_vis_data
      - cp_vis_mgt
endPoints:
  - endPointId: cp_tracker_ext_in
    external: true
    management: false
    ranConnection: true
  - endPointId: cp_tracker_data
    external: false
    management: false
    ranConnection: false
  - endPointId: cp_tracker_mgt
    external: true
    management: true
    ranConnection: false
  - endPointId: cp_vis_data
    external: false
    management: false
    ranConnection: false
  - endPointId: cp_vis_mgt
    external: true
    management: true
    ranConnection: false
  - endPointId: sap_tracking_mobile
    external: true
    management: false
    ranConnection: true
  - endPointId: sap_tracking_mgt
    external: true
    management: true
    ranConnection: false
```

```
connectivityServices:
- endPointIds:
  - sap_tracking_mobile
  - cp_tracker_ext_in
  external: true
- endPointIds:
  - cp_vis_data
  - cp_tracker_data
  external: false
- endPointIds:
  - sap_tracking_mgt
  - cp_vis_mgt
  - cp_tracker_mgt
  external: true
compatibleContextBlueprint:
- 'ctx_delay'
- 'ctx_bg_traffic'
applicationMetrics:
- metricId: tracked_devices
  name: Number of total tracked devices
  metricCollectionType: CUMULATIVE
  unit: devices
  interval: 5s
  topic: /app/tracked_devices
- metricId: processed_records
  name: Number of total processed records
  metricCollectionType: CUMULATIVE
  unit: records
  interval: 5s
  topic: /app/processed_records
- metricId: tracking_response_time
  name: Max response time in milliseconds
  metricCollectionType: GAUGE
  unit: ms
  interval: 1s
  topic: /app/tracking_response_time
- metricId: tracking_memory_usage
  name: Memory usage in %
  metricCollectionType: GAUGE
  unit: '%'
  interval: 1s
  topic: /app/tracking_memory_usage
compatibleSites:
- ITALY_TURIN
```

Annex B – NSD example in ETSI NFV-IFA 014 format

NSD in ETSI NFV-IFA 014 [2] format for Ares2T tracking service use-case:

```
# vsb_ares2t_tracker_nsd.yaml
---
- nsdIdentifier: ns_ares2t_tracker
  designer: NXW
  version: '1.0'
  nsdName: ARES2T Tracker Service @ 5GEVE
  nsdInvariantId: ns_ares2t_tracker_v1.0
  vnfdId:
    - c84b227e-520e-43c0-a75e-e52781dd54dd
    - 419b1884-aea1-4cad-8647-c2cec55287b9
    - 51c420e3-c83d-4ce9-a5bf-0dbe339b351d
  sapd:
    - cpdId: sap_tracking_mobile
      description: SAP towards mobile equipment
      layerProtocol: IPV4
      cpRole: ROOT
      addressData:
        - addressType: IP_ADDRESS
          ipAddressAssignment: false
          floatingIpActivated: true
          ipAddressType: IPv4
          numberOfIpAddress: 1
      sapAddressAssignment: false
      nsVirtualLinkDescId: vl_tracking_mobile
    - cpdId: sap_tracking_mgt
      description: SAP for management
      layerProtocol: IPV4
      cpRole: ROOT
      addressData:
        - addressType: IP_ADDRESS
          ipAddressAssignment: false
          floatingIpActivated: false
          ipAddressType: IPv4
          numberOfIpAddress: 1
      sapAddressAssignment: false
      nsVirtualLinkDescId: vl_tracking_mgt
  virtualLinkDesc:
    - virtualLinkDescId: vl_tracking_mobile
      virtualLinkDescProvider: NXW
      virtualLinkDescVersion: '1.0'
      connectivityType:
        layerProtocol: IPV4
      virtualLinkDf:
        - flavourId: df_vl_tracking_mobile
          qos:
            latency: 0
            packetDelayVariation: 0
            packetLossRatio: 0
            priority: 0
            serviceAvailabilityLevel: LEVEL_1
          description: Network to connect to the mobile user equipment
    - virtualLinkDescId: vl_tracking_mgt
      virtualLinkDescProvider: NXW
      virtualLinkDescVersion: '1.0'
      connectivityType:
        layerProtocol: IPV4
```

```

virtualLinkDf:
  - flavourId: df_vl_tracking_mgt
    qos:
      latency: 0
      packetDelayVariation: 0
      packetLossRatio: 0
      priority: 0
      serviceAvailabilityLevel: LEVEL_1
    description: Management network
- virtualLinkDescId: vl_tracking_data
  virtualLinkDescProvider: NXW
  virtualLinkDescVersion: '1.0'
  connectivityType:
    layerProtocol: IPV4
  virtualLinkDf:
    - flavourId: df_vl_tracking_data
      qos:
        latency: 0
        packetDelayVariation: 0
        packetLossRatio: 0
        priority: 0
        serviceAvailabilityLevel: LEVEL_1
      description: Internal network to connect the tracking service components
nsDf:
- nsDfId: ns_Ares2T_Tracking_df
  flavourKey: ns_Ares2T_Tracking_df_fk
  vnfProfile:
    - vnfProfileId: vnfp_small_Ares2T_Tracker
      vnfId: 419b1884-aea1-4cad-8647-c2cec55287b9
      flavourId: vnf_df_Ares2T_Tracker
      instantiationLevel: vnf_il_Ares2T_Tracker
      minNumberOfInstances: 1
      maxNumberOfInstances: 1
      nsVirtualLinkConnectivity:
        - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_mobile
          cpdId:
            - cp_tracker_ext_in
        - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_data
          cpdId:
            - cp_tracker_data
        - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_mgt
          cpdId:
            - cp_tracker_mgt
    - vnfProfileId: vnfp_big_Ares2T_Tracker
      vnfId: c84b227e-520e-43c0-a75e-e52781dd54dd
      flavourId: vnf_df_Ares2T_Tracker
      instantiationLevel: vnf_il_Ares2T_Tracker
      minNumberOfInstances: 1
      maxNumberOfInstances: 1
      nsVirtualLinkConnectivity:
        - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_mobile
          cpdId:
            - cp_tracker_ext_in
        - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_data
          cpdId:
            - cp_tracker_data
        - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_mgt
          cpdId:
            - cp_tracker_mgt
    - vnfProfileId: vnfp_Ares2T_Vis
      vnfId: 51c420e3-c83d-4ce9-a5bf-0dbe339b351d

```

```

    flavourId: vnf_df_Ares2T_Vis
    instantiationLevel: vnf_il_Ares2T_Vis
    minNumberOfInstances: 1
    maxNumberOfInstances: 1
    nsVirtualLinkConnectivity:
      - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_data
        cpdId:
          - cp_vis_data
      - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_mgt
        cpdId:
          - cp_vis_mgt
  virtualLinkProfile:
    - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_mobile
      virtualLinkDescId: vl_tracking_mobile
      flavourId: df_vl_tracking_mobile
      maxBitrateRequirements:
        root: '1'
        leaf: '1'
      minBitrateRequirements:
        root: '1'
        leaf: '1'
    - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_data
      virtualLinkDescId: vl_tracking_data
      flavourId: df_vl_tracking_data
      maxBitrateRequirements:
        root: '1'
        leaf: '1'
      minBitrateRequirements:
        root: '1'
        leaf: '1'
    - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_mgt
      virtualLinkDescId: vl_tracking_mgt
      flavourId: df_vl_tracking_mgt
      maxBitrateRequirements:
        root: '1'
        leaf: '1'
      minBitrateRequirements:
        root: '1'
        leaf: '1'
  nsInstantiationLevel:
    - nsLevelId: ns_ares2t_tracker_il_big
      description: Big instantiation level for the ARES2T tracking service
      vnfToLevelMapping:
        - vnfProfileId: vnfp_big_Ares2T_Tracker
          numberOfInstances: 1
        - vnfProfileId: vnfp_Ares2T_Vis
          numberOfInstances: 1
      virtualLinkToLevelMapping:
        - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_mobile
          bitrateRequirements:
            root: '1'
            leaf: '1'
        - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_data
          bitrateRequirements:
            root: '1'
            leaf: '1'
        - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_mgt
          bitrateRequirements:
            root: '1'
            leaf: '1'
    - nsLevelId: ns_ares2t_tracker_il_small

```

```
description: Small instantiation level for the ARES2T tracking service
vnfToLevelMapping:
  - vnfProfileId: vnfp_small_Ares2T_Tracker
    numberOfInstances: 1
  - vnfProfileId: vnfp_Ares2T_Vis
    numberOfInstances: 1
virtualLinkToLevelMapping:
  - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_mobile
    bitRateRequirements:
      root: '1'
      leaf: '1'
  - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_data
    bitRateRequirements:
      root: '1'
      leaf: '1'
  - virtualLinkProfileId: vlp_vl_tracking_mgt
    bitRateRequirements:
      root: '1'
      leaf: '1'
defaultNsInstantiationLevelId: ns_ares2t_tracker_il_small
dependencies: []
security:
  signature: FC_NSD_SIGNATURE
  algorithm: FC_NSD_ALGORITHM
  certificate: FC_NSD_CERTIFICATE
```

Annex C – NSD example in ETSI NFV-SOL 001 format

NSD for the Ares2T Tracking use-case translated from NFV-IFA to NFV-SOL format by the portal catalogue. Only the one instantiation level is shown (“ns_ares2t_tracker_il_big”).

```
# nsd_sol001_ares2t_tracker.yaml
---
toscaDefinitionsVersion: "tosca_simple_yaml_1_2"
toscaDefaultNamespace: "toscanfv"
description: "Big instantiation level for the ARES2T tracking service"
metadata:
  descriptorId: "00c56c7e-4ef4-392e-8be6-51e459997547"
  vendor: "NXW"
  version: "1.0"
topologyTemplate:
  substitutionMappings:
    nodeType: "tosca.nodes.nfv.NS"
  requirements:
    virtualLink:
      - cp: "sap_tracking_mobile"
        vl: "vl_tracking_mobile"
      - cp: "sap_tracking_mgt"
        vl: "vl_tracking_mgt"
  nodeTemplates:
    51c420e3-c83d-4ce9-a5bf-0dbe339b351d: !<tosca.nodes.nfv.VNF>
      type: "tosca.nodes.nfv.VNF"
      properties:
        descriptorId: "51c420e3-c83d-4ce9-a5bf-0dbe339b351d"
        descriptorVersion: "1.0"
        provider: "NXW"
        productName: "51c420e3-c83d-4ce9-a5bf-0dbe339b351d"
        softwareVersion: "1.0"
        productInfoName: null
        productInfoDescription: null
        defaultLocalizationLanguage: null
        flavourId: "vnf_df_Ares2T_Vis"
        flavourDescription: null
        vnfProfile: "vnfp_Ares2T_Vis"
      requirements:
        virtualLink:
          cp_vis_data: "vl_tracking_data"
          cp_vis_mgt: "vl_tracking_mgt"
        vl_tracking_mobile: !<tosca.nodes.nfv.NsVirtualLink>
          type: "tosca.nodes.nfv.NsVirtualLink"
          properties:
            description: "Network to connect to the mobile user equipment"
            vlProfile: {}
        vl_tracking_mgt: !<tosca.nodes.nfv.NsVirtualLink>
          type: "tosca.nodes.nfv.NsVirtualLink"
          properties:
            description: "Management network"
            vlProfile: {}
    ns_ares2t_tracker_ns_Ares2T_Tracking_df_ns_ares2t_tracker_il_big:
      !<tosca.nodes.nfv.NS>
      type: "tosca.nodes.nfv.NS"
      properties:
        descriptorId: "00c56c7e-4ef4-392e-8be6-51e459997547"
        designer: "NXW"
        version: "1.0"
        name: "ns_ares2t_tracker_ns_Ares2T_Tracking_df_ns_ares2t_tracker_il_big"
```

```
    invariantId: "ns_ares2t_tracker_v1.0_ns_Ares2T_Track-
ing_df_ns_ares2t_tracker_il_big"
  requirements:
    virtualLink:
      - "vl_tracking_mobile"
      - "vl_tracking_data"
      - "vl_tracking_mgt"
c84b227e-520e-43c0-a75e-e52781dd54dd: !<tosca.nodes.nfv.VNF>
type: "tosca.nodes.nfv.VNF"
properties:
  descriptorId: "c84b227e-520e-43c0-a75e-e52781dd54dd"
  descriptorVersion: "1.0"
  provider: "NXW"
  productName: "c84b227e-520e-43c0-a75e-e52781dd54dd"
  softwareVersion: "1.0"
  productInfoName: null
  productInfoDescription: null
  defaultLocalizationLanguage: null
  flavourId: "vnf_df_Ares2T_Tracker"
  flavourDescription: null
  vnfProfile: "vnfp_big_Ares2T_Tracker"
requirements:
  virtualLink:
    cp_tracker_mgt: "vl_tracking_mgt"
    cp_tracker_ext_in: "vl_tracking_mobile"
    cp_tracker_data: "vl_tracking_data"
vl_tracking_data: !<tosca.nodes.nfv.NsVirtualLink>
type: "tosca.nodes.nfv.NsVirtualLink"
properties:
  description: "Internal network to connect the tracking service components"
  vlProfile: {}
```

Annex D – Translation Rules example

Translation rules for Ares2T tracking service use-case:

```
# vsb_ares2t_tracker_tr.yaml
---
- nsdId: ns_ares2t_tracker
  nsdVersion: '1.0'
  nsFlavourId: ns_Ares2T_Tracking_df
  nsInstantiationLevelId: ns_ares2t_tracker_il_small
  input:
    - parameterId: number_of_tracked_devices
      minValue: '1'
      maxValue: '100'
- nsdId: ns_ares2t_tracker
  nsdVersion: '1.0'
  nsFlavourId: ns_Ares2T_Tracking_df
  nsInstantiationLevelId: ns_ares2t_tracker_il_big
  input:
    - parameterId: number_of_tracked_devices
      minValue: '101'
      maxValue: '1000'
```

Annex E – CtxB example

CtxB example for a traffic delay generator:

```
# ctx_delay.yaml
---
blueprintId: 'ctx_delay'
version: '1.0'
name: Delay Generator
description: NETEM Traffic Delay Generator Service
parameters:
  - parameterId: incoming_traffic_load
    parameterName: Incoming Traffic Load
    parameterType: number
    parameterDescription: Maximum bw of the incoming traffic in Mbps
    applicabilityField: Traffic shaping
configurableParameters:
  - delay_avg
  - delay_var
  - consecutive_delay_dependency_percentage
atomicComponents:
  - componentId: delay_generator
    serversNumber: 1
    endPointsIds:
      - cp_dg_traffic_in
      - cp_dg_traffic_out
      - cp_dg_mgt
endPoints:
  - endPointId: cp_dg_traffic_in
    external: true
    management: false
    ranConnection: true
  - endPointId: cp_dg_traffic_out
    external: true
    management: false
    ranConnection: false
  - endPointId: cp_dg_mgt
    external: true
    management: true
    ranConnection: false
  - endPointId: sap_dg_in
    external: true
    management: false
    ranConnection: true
  - endPointId: sap_dg_out
    external: true
    management: false
    ranConnection: false
  - endPointId: sap_dg_mgt
    external: true
    management: true
    ranConnection: false
compatibleSites:
  - ITALY_TURIN
connectivityServices:
  - endPointIds:
      - sap_dg_mgt
      - cp_dg_mgt
    external: true
  - endPointIds:
```

```

    - sap_dg_out
    - cp_dg_traffic_out
  external: true
- endPointIds:
  - sap_dg_in
  - cp_dg_traffic_in
  external: true
applicationMetrics:
- metricId: 'delay_iface'
  name: 'Traffic delay measured between In and Out interfaces'
  metricCollectionType: 'GAUGE'
  unit: 'ms'
  interval: '1s'
  topic: '/app/delay_iface'

```

CtxB example for a background traffic generator:

```

# ctx_bg_traffic.yaml
---
blueprintId: 'ctx_bg_traffic'
version: '1.0'
name: 'Context Blueprint Background Traffic'
description: 'Context Blueprint to add artificial background traffic to a VSB.'
parameters:
  - parameterId: 'bg_traffic_rate'
    parameterName: 'Background Traffic rate'
    parameterType: 'number'
    parameterDescription: 'The amount of background traffic in Mbps.'
    applicabilityField: Traffic shaping
configurableParameters:
  - 'bg_traffic_rate'
atomicComponents:
  - componentId: bg_traffic_src
    serversNumber: 1
    endPointIds:
      - cp_bg_src_data
      - cp_bg_src_mgmt
  - componentId: bg_traffic_dst
    serversNumber: 1
    endPointIds:
      - cp_bg_dst_data
      - cp_bg_dst_mgmt
endPoints:
  - endPointId: cp_bg_src_data
    external: false
    management: false
    ranConnection: false
  - endPointId: cp_bg_src_mgmt
    external: false
    management: true
    ranConnection: false
  - endPointId: cp_bg_dst_data
    external: false
    management: false
    ranConnection: false
  - endPointId: cp_bg_dst_mgmt
    external: false
    management: true
    ranConnection: false
  - endPointId: sap_bg_mgmt
    external: true

```

```
management: true
ranConnection: false
connectivityServices:
- endPointIds:
  - cp_bg_src_data
  - cp_bg_dst_data
- endPointIds:
  - cp_bg_src_mgmt
  - cp_bg_dst_mgmt
  - sap_bg_mgmt
applicationMetrics:
- metricId: 'traffic_rate_dst'
  name: 'Traffic rate measured at DST'
  metricCollectionType: 'GAUGE'
  unit: 'Mbps'
  interval: '2s'
  topic: '/app/traffic_rate'
- metricId: 'lost_packets'
  name: 'Lost packets between SRC and DST'
  metricCollectionType: 'CUMULATIVE'
  unit: 'count'
  interval: '5s'
  topic: '/app/lost_packets'
```

Annex F - TcB example

TcB example for a test execution:

```
# tcb_ares2t_tracker_1.yaml
---
testcaseBlueprintId: 'ares2t_testcase_1'
version: '1.0'
name: TCB Ares2T Tracking with delay
description: Test case to run the Ares2T tracking service with traffic delay
script: "sudo tc qdisc add dev eth2 root netem delay $$var$$delay\
 \ $$var$$delay_var $$var$$dep%"
userParameters:
  delay: $$var$$delay
  delay variance: $$var$$delay_var
  consecutive delay dependency percentage: $$var$$dep
infrastructureParameters:
  ns.nsd_id.vnf.vnfd_id.cp.cpId1.idAddr: '$$varX'
  ns.nsd_id.vnf.vnfd_id.cp.cpId2.idAddr: '$$varY'
```

Annex G – ExpB example

ExpB example for the Ares2T Tracking service use-case composed with the artificial delay context.

```
# expb_ares2t_tracker.yaml
---
expBlueprintId: 'expb_ares2t_tracker'
version: '1.0'
name: Ares2T tracking experiment
description: Ares2T tracking service with delay experiment
sites:
  - ITALY_TURIN
kpis:
  - kpiId: 'kpi_tracking_response_time'
    name: 'Response time must be lower than or equal to the objective.'
    formula: 'tracking_response_time'
    unit: 'ms'
    interval: '1s'
    metricIds: ['tracking_response_time']
  - kpiId: 'kpi_memory_usage'
    name: 'Memory usage must be lower than or equal to the objective.'
    formula: 'tracking_memory_usage'
    unit: 'MB'
    interval: '1s'
    metricIds: ['tracking_memory_usage']
metrics:
  - metricId: 'cpu_consumption'
    name: 'Measurement of CPU consumption.'
    metricCollectionType: 'GAUGE'
    unit: '%'
    interval: '1s'
    iMetricType: 'CPU_CONSUMPTION'
  - metricId: 'memory_consumption'
    name: 'Measurement of memory consumption.'
    metricCollectionType: 'GAUGE'
    unit: 'GB'
    interval: '1s'
    iMetricType: 'MEMORY_CONSUMPTION'
vsBlueprintId: 'vsb_ares2t_tracker'
ctxBlueprintIds:
  - 'ctx_delay'
  - 'ctx_bg_traffic'
tcBlueprintIds:
  - 'ares2t_testcase_1'
```

Annex H - ExpD example

ExpD example for Ares2T tracking service use-case:

```
# expd_ares2t_tracker.yaml
---
expDescriptorId: "expd_ares2t_tracker_0001"
name: "ExpD for the Ares2T Tracker experiment."
version: "1.0"
expBlueprintId: "expb_ares2t_tracker"
vsDescriptorId: "vsd_ares2t_tracker_0001"
ctxDescriptorIds:
  - "ctxd_netem_ares2t_tracker_0001"
  - "ctxd_bgtraffic_ares2t_tracker_0001"
testCaseDescriptorIds:
  - "tcd_ares2t_testcase_1"
kpiThresholds:
  kpi_tracking_response_time: "20ms"
```

Annex I – NSD generated by the ENC

NSD example generated by the ENC by composing the Ares2T Transport Tracker service with the artificial delay context and the background traffic generator context.

```
# expb_ares2t_tracker_nsds.yaml
---
nsdIdentifier: "ns_ares2t_tracker"
designer: "NXW"
version: "1.0"
nsdName: "ARES2T Tracker Service @ 5GEVE + NETEM Traffic Delay Generator Service
+\
 \ Context Blueprint Background Traffic_nsd"
nsdInvariantId: "ns_ares2t_tracker_v1.0"
vnfdId:
- "c84b227e-520e-43c0-a75e-e52781dd54dd"
- "419b1884-aea1-4cad-8647-c2cec55287b9"
- "51c420e3-c83d-4ce9-a5bf-0dbe339b351d"
- "396d1b6b-331b-4dd7-b48e-376517d3654a"
- "bg_traffic_src"
- "bg_traffic_dst"
sapd:
- cpdId: "sap_tracking_mobile"
  layerProtocol: "IPV4"
  cpRole: "ROOT"
  description: "SAP towards mobile equipment"
  addressData:
  - addressType: "IP_ADDRESS"
    ipAddressAssignment: false
    floatingIpActivated: true
    management: false
    ipAddressType: "IPv4"
    numberOfIpAddress: 1
    sapAddressAssignment: false
    nsVirtualLinkDescId: "vl_tracking_mobile"
- cpdId: "sap_tracking_mgt"
  layerProtocol: "IPV4"
  cpRole: "ROOT"
  description: "SAP for management"
  addressData:
  - addressType: "IP_ADDRESS"
    ipAddressAssignment: false
    floatingIpActivated: false
    management: false
    ipAddressType: "IPv4"
    numberOfIpAddress: 1
    sapAddressAssignment: false
    nsVirtualLinkDescId: "vl_tracking_mgt"
virtualLinkDesc:
- virtualLinkDescId: "vl_tracking_mobile"
  virtualLinkDescProvider: "NXW"
  virtualLinkDescVersion: "1.0"
  connectivityType:
    layerProtocol: "IPV4"
    flowPattern: null
  virtualLinkDf:
  - flavourId: "df_vl_tracking_mobile"
    qos:
      latency: 0
```

```
    packetDelayVariation: 0
    packetLossRatio: 0
    priority: 0
    serviceAvailabilityLevel: "LEVEL_1"
    description: "Network to connect to the mobile user equipment"
- virtualLinkDescId: "vl_tracking_mgt"
  virtualLinkDescProvider: "NXW"
  virtualLinkDescVersion: "1.0"
  connectivityType:
    layerProtocol: "IPV4"
    flowPattern: null
  virtualLinkDf:
- flavourId: "df_vl_tracking_mgt"
  qos:
    latency: 0
    packetDelayVariation: 0
    packetLossRatio: 0
    priority: 0
    serviceAvailabilityLevel: "LEVEL_1"
    description: "Management network"
- virtualLinkDescId: "vl_tracking_data"
  virtualLinkDescProvider: "NXW"
  virtualLinkDescVersion: "1.0"
  connectivityType:
    layerProtocol: "IPV4"
    flowPattern: null
  virtualLinkDf:
- flavourId: "df_vl_tracking_data"
  qos:
    latency: 0
    packetDelayVariation: 0
    packetLossRatio: 0
    priority: 0
    serviceAvailabilityLevel: "LEVEL_1"
    description: "Internal network to connect the tracking service components"
- virtualLinkDescId: "vl_dg_out"
  virtualLinkDescProvider: "NXW"
  virtualLinkDescVersion: "1.0"
  connectivityType:
    layerProtocol: "IPV4"
    flowPattern: null
  virtualLinkDf:
- flavourId: "df_vl_dg_out"
  qos:
    latency: 0
    packetDelayVariation: 0
    packetLossRatio: 0
    priority: 0
    serviceAvailabilityLevel: "LEVEL_1"
    description: "Network to send outgoing delayed traffic."
nsDf:
- nsDfId: "ns_Ares2T_Tracking_df"
  flavourKey: "ns_Ares2T_Tracking_df_fk"
  vnfProfile:
- vnfProfileId: "vnfp_small_Ares2T_Tracker"
  vnfId: "419b1884-aea1-4cad-8647-c2cec55287b9"
  flavourId: "vnf_df_Ares2T_Tracker"
  instantiationLevel: "vnf_il_Ares2T_Tracker"
  minNumberOfInstances: 1
  maxNumberOfInstances: 1
  nsVirtualLinkConnectivity:
```

```
- virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_dg_out"
  cpdId:
  - "cp_tracker_ext_in"
- virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_data"
  cpdId:
  - "cp_tracker_data"
- virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mgt"
  cpdId:
  - "cp_tracker_mgt"
- vnfProfileId: "vnfp_big_Ares2T_Tracker"
  vnfdId: "c84b227e-520e-43c0-a75e-e52781dd54dd"
  flavourId: "vnf_df_Ares2T_Tracker"
  instantiationLevel: "vnf_il_Ares2T_Tracker"
  minNumberOfInstances: 1
  maxNumberOfInstances: 1
  nsVirtualLinkConnectivity:
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_dg_out"
    cpdId:
    - "cp_tracker_ext_in"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_data"
    cpdId:
    - "cp_tracker_data"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mgt"
    cpdId:
    - "cp_tracker_mgt"
- vnfProfileId: "vnfp_Ares2T_Vis"
  vnfdId: "51c420e3-c83d-4ce9-a5bf-0dbe339b351d"
  flavourId: "vnf_df_Ares2T_Vis"
  instantiationLevel: "vnf_il_Ares2T_Vis"
  minNumberOfInstances: 1
  maxNumberOfInstances: 1
  nsVirtualLinkConnectivity:
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_data"
    cpdId:
    - "cp_vis_data"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mgt"
    cpdId:
    - "cp_vis_mgt"
- vnfProfileId: "vnfp_netem"
  vnfdId: "396d1b6b-331b-4dd7-b48e-376517d3654a"
  flavourId: "vnf_df_netem"
  instantiationLevel: "vnf_il_netem"
  minNumberOfInstances: 1
  maxNumberOfInstances: 1
  nsVirtualLinkConnectivity:
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_dg_out"
    cpdId:
    - "cp_dg_traffic_out"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mgt"
    cpdId:
    - "cp_dg_mgt"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mobile"
    cpdId:
    - "cp_dg_traffic_in"
- vnfProfileId: "bg_traffic_src_vnfp"
  vnfdId: "bg_traffic_src"
  flavourId: "bg_traffic_src_vnf_df"
  instantiationLevel: "bg_traffic_src_vnf_il"
  minNumberOfInstances: 1
  maxNumberOfInstances: 1
  nsVirtualLinkConnectivity:
```

```

- virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mobile"
  cpdId:
  - "cp_bg_src_data"
- virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mgt"
  cpdId:
  - "cp_bg_src_mgmt"
- vnfProfileId: "bg_traffic_dst_vnfp"
  vnfId: "bg_traffic_dst"
  flavourId: "bg_traffic_dst_vnf_df"
  instantiationLevel: "bg_traffic_dst_vnf_il"
  minNumberOfInstances: 1
  maxNumberOfInstances: 1
  nsVirtualLinkConnectivity:
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_data"
    cpdId:
    - "cp_bg_dst_data"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mgt"
    cpdId:
    - "cp_bg_dst_mgmt"
virtualLinkProfile:
- virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mobile"
  virtualLinkDescId: "vl_tracking_mobile"
  flavourId: "df_vl_tracking_mobile"
  maxBitrateRequirements:
    root: "1"
    leaf: "1"
  minBitrateRequirements:
    root: "1"
    leaf: "1"
- virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_data"
  virtualLinkDescId: "vl_tracking_data"
  flavourId: "df_vl_tracking_data"
  maxBitrateRequirements:
    root: "1"
    leaf: "1"
  minBitrateRequirements:
    root: "1"
    leaf: "1"
- virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mgt"
  virtualLinkDescId: "vl_tracking_mgt"
  flavourId: "df_vl_tracking_mgt"
  maxBitrateRequirements:
    root: "1"
    leaf: "1"
  minBitrateRequirements:
    root: "1"
    leaf: "1"
- virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_dg_out"
  virtualLinkDescId: "vl_dg_out"
  flavourId: "df_vl_dg_out"
  maxBitrateRequirements:
    root: "1"
    leaf: "1"
  minBitrateRequirements:
    root: "1"
    leaf: "1"
nsInstantiationLevel:
- nsLevelId: "ns_ares2t_tracker_il_big"
  description: "Big instantiation level for the ARES2T tracking service"
  vnfToLevelMapping:
  - vnfProfileId: "vnfp_big_Ares2T_Tracker"

```

```

    numberOfInstances: 1
  - vnfProfileId: "vnfp_Ares2T_Vis"
    numberOfInstances: 1
  - vnfProfileId: "vnfp_netem"
    numberOfInstances: 1
  - vnfProfileId: "bg_traffic_src_vnfp"
    numberOfInstances: 1
  - vnfProfileId: "bg_traffic_dst_vnfp"
    numberOfInstances: 1
  virtualLinkToLevelMapping:
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mobile"
    bitRateRequirements:
      root: "1"
      leaf: "1"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_data"
    bitRateRequirements:
      root: "1"
      leaf: "1"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mgt"
    bitRateRequirements:
      root: "1"
      leaf: "1"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_dg_out"
    bitRateRequirements:
      root: "1"
      leaf: "1"
- nsLevelId: "ns_ares2t_tracker_il_small"
  description: "Small instantiation level for the ARES2T tracking service"
  vnfToLevelMapping:
  - vnfProfileId: "vnfp_small_Ares2T_Tracker"
    numberOfInstances: 1
  - vnfProfileId: "vnfp_Ares2T_Vis"
    numberOfInstances: 1
  - vnfProfileId: "vnfp_netem"
    numberOfInstances: 1
  - vnfProfileId: "bg_traffic_src_vnfp"
    numberOfInstances: 1
  - vnfProfileId: "bg_traffic_dst_vnfp"
    numberOfInstances: 1
  virtualLinkToLevelMapping:
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mobile"
    bitRateRequirements:
      root: "1"
      leaf: "1"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_data"
    bitRateRequirements:
      root: "1"
      leaf: "1"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_tracking_mgt"
    bitRateRequirements:
      root: "1"
      leaf: "1"
  - virtualLinkProfileId: "vlp_vl_dg_out"
    bitRateRequirements:
      root: "1"
      leaf: "1"
  defaultNsInstantiationLevelId: "ns_ares2t_tracker_il_small"
  security:
    signature: "FC_NSD_SIGNATURE"
    algorithm: "FC_NSD_ALGORITHM"
    certificate: "FC_NSD_CERTIFICATE"

```

Annex J – Example of requests received by the DCM from the ELM

This example is based on the metrics and KPIs from the VSB, CtxB and ExpB examples provided in Annex A, Annex E, and Annex G, showing the transformations performed by the ELM for providing all the monitoring data to the DCM through its API, using the *publish* operation (*POST /dcm/publish/<signalling topic>*).

This case is based on the subscription phase, so the *action* field is set to “subscribe”. In case of being in the withdrawal phase, the *action* field would be set to “unsubscribe”. Both phases are defined in deliverable D3.3 [12].

```
POST /dcm/publish/signalling.metric.application
```

```
{
  'records': [{
    'value': {
      'expId': '1',
      'action': 'subscribe',
      'topic': '1.italy_turin.application_metric.tracked_devices',
      'context': {
        'metricId': 'tracked_devices',
        'name': 'Number of total tracked devices',
        'metricCollectionType': 'CUMULATIVE',
        'unit': 'devices',
        'interval': '5s',
        'topic': '/app/tracked_devices'
      }
    }
  },
  {
    'value': {
      'expId': '1',
      'action': 'subscribe',
      'topic': '1.italy_turin.application_metric.processed_records',
      'context': {
        'metricId': 'processed_records',
        'name': 'Number of total processed records',
        'metricCollectionType': 'CUMULATIVE',
        'unit': 'records',
        'interval': '5s',
        'topic': '/app/processed_records'
      }
    }
  },
  {
    'value': {
      'expId': '1',
      'action': 'subscribe',
      'topic': '1.italy_turin.application_metric.tracking_response_time',
      'context': {
        'metricId': 'tracking_response_time',
        'name': 'Max response time in milliseconds',
        'metricCollectionType': 'GAUGE',
        'unit': 'ms',
        'interval': '1s',
        'topic': '/app/tracking_response_time'
      }
    }
  }
},
```

```

    {
      'value': {
        'expId': '1',
        'action': 'subscribe',
        'topic': '1.italy_turin.application_metric.tracking_memory_usage',
        'context': {
          'metricId': 'tracking_memory_usage',
          'name': 'Memory usage in %',
          'metricCollectionType': 'GAUGE',
          'unit': '%',
          'interval': '1s',
          'topic': '/app/tracking_memory_usage'
        }
      }
    },
    {
      'value': {
        'expId': '1',
        'action': 'subscribe',
        'topic': '1.italy_turin.application_metric.delay_iface',
        'context': {
          'metricId': 'delay_iface',
          'name': 'Traffic delay measured between In and Out interfaces',
          'metricCollectionType': 'GAUGE',
          'unit': 'ms',
          'interval': '1s',
          'topic': '/app/delay_iface'
        }
      }
    }
  ]
}

POST /dcm/publish/signalling.metric.infrastructure

{
  'records': [{
    'value': {
      'expId': '1',
      'action': 'subscribe',
      'topic': '1.italy_turin.infrastructure_metric.cpu_consumption',
      'context': {
        'metricId': 'cpu_consumption',
        'name': 'Measurement of CPU consumption.',
        'metricCollectionType': 'GAUGE',
        'unit': '%',
        'interval': '1s',
        'iMetricType': 'CPU_CONSUMPTION'
      }
    }
  },
  {
    'value': {
      'expId': '1',
      'action': 'subscribe',
      'topic': '1.italy_turin.infrastructure_metric.memory_consumption',
      'context': {
        'metricId': 'memory_consumption',
        'name': 'Measurement of memory consumption.',
        'metricCollectionType': 'GAUGE',
        'unit': 'GB',
        'interval': '1s',
      }
    }
  }
}

```

```
        'iMetricType': 'MEMORY_CONSUMPTION'
      }
    }
  ]]
}

POST /dcm/publish/signalling.kpi

{
  'records': [{
    'value': {
      'expId': '1',
      'action': 'subscribe',
      'topic': '1.italy_turin.kpi.kpi_tracking_response_time',
      'context': {
        'kpiId': 'kpi_tracking_response_time',
        'name': 'Response time must be lower than or equal to the objec-
tive.',
        'unit': 'ms',
        'interval': '1s'
      }
    }
  },
  {
    'value': {
      'expId': '1',
      'action': 'subscribe',
      'topic': '1.italy_turin.kpi.kpi_memory_usage',
      'context': {
        'kpiId': 'kpi_tracking_response_time',
        'name': 'Memory usage must be lower than or equal to the objec-
tive.',
        'unit': 'MB',
        'interval': '1s'
      }
    }
  }
  ]]
}
```

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